

APRIL 2023

**CARNIVAL
VOL. XXII**

JOURNAL OF THE
INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS OF HISTORY ASSOCIATION

ISSN: 2788-4074

Carnival (Journal of the International Students of History Association),
vol. 22, April 2023

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Carnival is a publication of ISHA, the International Students of History Association. Carnival is published online under the ISSN-Number 2788-4074. Former editions of Carnival have been published under the following ISSN-Numbers: 1457-1226; 1582-3261.

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Editorial

Dear ISHA members, dear readers,

We are delighted to present the latest edition of *Carnival*, a thematic issue that delves into the complexities of diplomacy and international relations. As Editors-in-Chief, we are proud to introduce this thematic issue, which features a collection of insightful articles from all over Europe.

This issue of *Carnival* focuses on the fascinating world of diplomacy and international relations, exploring the historical and contemporary challenges faced by nations in their interactions with each other. The articles featured in this edition provide a unique insight into various aspects of international relations, including the role of media and public opinion in foreign policy decision-making, the impact of diaspora engagement on international relations, and the early forms of European integration.

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Editorial Board of *Carnival* for their unwavering support and guidance throughout the publication process. Their commitment to excellence has been instrumental in bringing this thematic issue to fruition. We would also like to thank the authors for their exceptional contributions.

At a time when the world is facing unprecedented challenges, such as climate change, and geopolitical tensions, understanding the complexities of diplomacy and international relations is more important than ever. We believe that this issue of *Carnival* will provide readers with a deeper understanding of aspects of these complex issues, and inspire further research and discussion.

We invite you to explore this edition of *Carnival* and engage with the diverse perspectives presented in these articles. We hope that this thematic issue will inspire fruitful future talks.

With warm regards,

Charlotte Rottiers & Jeroen Petit

Press and Public Pressure in Foreign Affairs: The Case of Political Narratives in Newspapers and their extent to influence British and Austro–Hungarian Foreign Policy decision-making in the Great Eastern Crisis of 1875–1878¹

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Abstract

Political journals of the Great Powers and their audience were greatly interested in following the prelude of the Great Eastern Crisis and its climax, the Russo–Turkish War of 1877–1878. Two Empires outside the conflict especially considered Russian defeat a favourable outcome: Austria–Hungary and Britain. Anti-Russian and pro-Turkish sentiments were prominent within the bellicose agitations, that had shaken the domestic and external front of politics in both countries. While the legislative background of the press was vastly different in the two empires, the articles discussing the events of the war show a striking resemblance. Public opinion followed these narratives and manifested on the domestic frontier: by the autumn of 1876, thousands protested on the streets of Budapest, while similarly the followers of Gladstone and the opposing ‘jingoists’ took the streets of London and other cities. Using the theory of Edward Herman and Noam Chomsky (Manufactured Consent), and the conceptual framework of Foreign Policy Analysis, I hypothesise that while the Conservative British political elite could easily frame and amplify ideas by outlets like The Daily Telegraph, Daily News, Pall Mall Gazette, and The Times, Hungarian daily papers (Pesti Napló, Hon, Ellenőr, Egyetértés) could have adopted the oven-ready narrative to express and support their pro-Turkish/anti-Russian standpoint. The aim of this paper, therefore, is to observe the parallels between British and Hungarian political press, the adaptation of news and subsequently the reception by Hungarian newsreaders. Additionally, the paper is centred around the greater issue of public pressure on foreign policy decision-making. The paper aims to examine how the narrative of the British bellicose media was adopted in leading Hungarian newspapers, and how it was received and if it formulated domestic and foreign political frontiers.

¹ Fully funded by the ÚNKP-21-3 New National Excellence Program of the Hungarian Ministry for Innovation and Technology from the Source of the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund.

Introduction and context

After the international sensation of the 1870–1871 Franco–Prussian war and the subsequent German unification, a cholera epidemic (1872), a stock market crash (1873) and an economic crisis in its wake shook the European Great Powers. The 1875 uprising of Herzegovinian Slavic subjects of the Ottoman Empire happened partly as a result of the aforementioned crisis, but also because of the idea of ‘another’ unification war for the Pan-Slavic cause, after the Italian (1859-1861, 1871) and German (1866, 1870-1871) historical events. In the autumn of 1874, the Slavic Christian subjects of Herzegovina were incited by their local leaders to take up arms, and later in 1875, they asked semi-independent vassals of the Ottoman Empire such as Montenegro and Serbia to aid their cause.² In a matter of weeks, the conflict escalated into an international crisis and then determined the international affairs and media agenda of the Great Powers for almost three years, to be peacefully settled by the Berlin Congress of 1878. As an ally to the Pan-Slavic cause, Russia saw the opportunity in the conflict. After the 1856 Paris Treaty, Russian decision-makers strived to end the isolation of the country. By 1871, they had partly succeeded as the Treaty of London revised the Black Seas clauses of the treaty, and it revoked the neutral status of the Black Sea.³ In the years 1875–1876, Russian leadership wanted to get similar guarantees to divide the sphere of influence in the Balkans. In the spirit of the already existing alliance between Germany, Austria-Hungary and Russia – named as League of the Three Emperors (1873) – the Reichstadt Agreement (July 8, 1876) and later the Budapest Convention (January 15, 1877) were made in secret.⁴ In the case of a Turkish victory against their Slavic subjects, the former treaty proposed a *status quo ante bellum*. If the outcome of the

² *Balkán kronológia I. Birodalmak szorításában, 1700–1878*, ed. Demeter, Gábor (Budapest–Sofia: Institut za Istoricheski Izsledvaniya, BAN, Bölcsészettudományi Kutatóközpont, Történettudományi Intézet, 2020), 197-199.

³ France-Roy Bridge and Roger Bullen, *The Great Powers and the European States System 1814–1914* (Harlow: Pearson Education, 2005), 174-177.

⁴ István Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrássy. Magyarország a német hatalmi politikában a 19. század második felében* (Budapest, Vienna, München: Teleki Laszlo Stiftung, 1998), 205-212.

conflict would have favoured the insurgents, however, the Balkans would have been divided to a Western and Eastern sphere, accordingly to Austro-Hungarian and Russian interests, therefore avoiding direct conflict between the two Eastern powers. The Budapest Convention further reinforced the resolutions of the Reichstadt Treaty, and amended it with the prohibition of creating a large Slavic state.⁵ Despite all the precautions by the Austro-Hungarian diplomacy, as the talks at the 1876-1877 Constantinople Conference collapsed and Serbia was involved in the conflict, Tsar Alexander II saw military intervention fit, and the Russo-Turkish war came to reality on April 24, 1877.

During the crisis, the policy and international goals of Austria-Hungary were formulated by various levels of domestic actors and interests. At first glance, the Emperor and his minister of foreign affairs, Count Gyula Andrásy, along with the Viennese military circles were not interested in an anti-Russian political scheme and Andrásy gave his support to the Three Emperor's League.⁶ His former aides and the Hungarian political elite, however, did not see the political wisdom behind the alliance, nor did they accept even the slightest cooperation with a power supporting Slavic interests. In fear of losing the integrity of their multiethnic Kingdom, and because of the failure of the Hungarian revolution in 1849 – which was put down by Russian arms – the Hungarian elite strived to avoid the inclusion of even more Slavic-populated territories in the Dual Monarchy. The modern Hungarian political identity and attitude were therefore characterised by anti-Russian, and pro-Turkish sentiments.⁷ As a result of the Hungarian attitude, Andrásy had to find a way to follow the Emperor's policy, maintain the trust of his advisors, and appease or at least tone down the critical voices as much as in Hungary

⁵ Bridge and Bullen, *The Great Powers*, 201–203.

⁶ Vilmos Heiszler: *Az osztrák katonai vezetés és az Osztrák–Magyar Monarchia külpolitikája 1867–1882 között* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1984), 70-77.

⁷ Lajos Menyhárt, 'A három császár szövetsége és a magyar politikai közvélemény a keleti válság idején 1875–1878', *Acta Univ. Debrecensis. Series Historica* 5 (1966), 44.

as in the Cisleithanian legislative body, the *Reichsrat*.⁸ On the one hand, a pro-Russian policy could not only anger Hungarian public opinion but also with the victory of the Pan-Slavic movement could have had devastating effects on the integrity of the Monarchy. On the other hand, a strict anti-Russian policy could have endangered the alliance which provided the goodwill and alliance of the Monarchy's neighbours. To overcome these difficulties, on 31 December 1875, the so-called Andrassy Note was drafted, which contained a series of reforms for the rebellious principalities, without endangering the integrity of the Ottoman Empire. Ottoman leadership was desperate for a solution, as the state went bankrupt as early as October 1875, and creditors would not provide loans anymore.⁹ The integrity of the Empire therefore heavily depended on the goodwill and mediation of the bordering Great Powers.

Historiography, method and framework (foreign policy and frame analysis), limitations

The Great Eastern Crisis is a thoroughly discussed topic in historiography. From the range of books written on the British involvement in the affairs – such as the works of Seton-Watson, Harris, Millman, or Ković –, we can find several works on the history of Austro–Hungarian foreign affairs: G. H. Rupp examined the Austrian¹⁰ and Russian deals, István Diószegi studied German and Hungarian relations, and Rainer F. Schmidt discussed the failed alliance between Germany, Austria and England in his work.¹¹ However, these authors of the 20th century tended

⁸ József Zachar, *Az osztrák-német liberális Alkotmánypárt és a politikai hatalom: 1861-1881*, (Budapest: Akadémiai kiadó, 1981), 230-243.

⁹ Demeter, *Balkán kronológia*, 201.

¹⁰ In the case of the word *Austria* or *Austrian* the paper will employ the term to denote the Austro-Hungarian state or its leadership. As contemporary newspapers and diplomatic documents also rather use the term 'Austria' to refer to the entire state in diplomatic context, for the purpose of distinction I will use the historical concept of 'Cisleithania' or 'Cisleithanian Austria' to denote the territories of the Empire excluding the Hungarian Kingdom.

¹¹ R. W. Seton-Watson, *Disraeli, Gladstone, and the Eastern Question* (London: Macmillan & Co., 1935); David Harris, *A Diplomatic History of the Balkan Crisis of 1875–1878. The First Year* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1936); Richard Millman, *Britain and the Eastern Question. 1875–1878* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1979); Milos Ković, *Disraeli and the Eastern Question* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011); George Hoover Rupp, *A Wavering Friendship. Russia and Austria 1876-1878* (Philadelphia: Porcupine Press, 1978); Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrassy*; Rainer F. Schmidt, *Die gescheiterte Allianz: Österreich-Ungarn, England und das Deutsche Reich in der Ära Andrassy (1867 bis 1878/79)* (Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang, 1992).

to adopt the viewpoint of a specific state, with little regard for different domestic factors of foreign policy. Therefore, by uncovering the motives behind the public opinion which have affected foreign policy, we aim to complement the existing literature on Austro-Hungarian state affairs.¹²

In the late days of October 1876, students took the streets in Budapest, while a couple of months later, in Britain, pro-government demonstrations occurred in London and other major cities. Later in 1878, Britain and Austria-Hungary closely cooperated to dismantle Russian gains in the Balkans and threatened Russia with Anglo-Austrian cooperation in an upcoming war.¹³ But if Austria was allied with Russia, how did these events occur in such a paralleled fashion, and what could have influenced Austrian decision-makers? The paper aims to examine how the narrative of the British bellicose media was adopted in leading Hungarian newspapers, and if it formulated domestic and foreign policies. Therefore the paper applies two methods: one to examine the discourses within leading Hungarian and British outlets, and the other one to help to interpret the findings of the former method on a policy level.

To observe the parallels between British and Hungarian political press the paper employs frame analysis. Framing refers to the process of how we organize our data, categorizing events, names and all other elements of a story, i.e. a narrative. Part of the process is to find certain discursive cues which would help identify certain patterns in explanations, solutions, context, types of language, definitions or labels, historical association, metaphors, and moral appeals.¹⁴ In the analysis, we identify British-originated news in Hungarian outlets (e.g. *Pesti Napló*, *Hon*,

¹² See: Menyhárt, 'A három császár szövetsége', 43-63; Tamás Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások Budapesten a dualizmus első évtizedeiben 1873–1903*, (PhD diss., Eötvös Loránd University, 2010).

¹³ Schmidt, *Die gescheiterte Allianz*, 383-420.

¹⁴ Jenny Kitzinger, 'Framing and Frame Analysis', in *Media Studies: Key Issues and Debates*, ed. Eoin Devereux (London: Sage Publishers, 2007), 134-161.

Ellenőr, Egyetértés), track it back to the source material – British press coverage of a certain event or article – and look for cues whether it adopted a similar view on the issue. The criteria of the selection of British and Hungarian news articles were the following: a.) there was an implicit or explicit reference to a British article, correspondence, telegram, parliamentary or other political speech in one or more of the indicated Hungarian newspapers, and b.) British news articles which mentioned Austria-Hungary in regard to the crisis or what agency it ought to have – even if it was not referenced in Hungarian outlets. The latter criterion highlights the limitation of the research. No matter the strive for an accurate historical account, we cannot for certain state that public opinion was influenced only by political articles and British agents of media alone, neither can we state that British opinion on Austria reached the public exclusively through the channels of Hungarian outlets. We have to consider that aside from the Hungarian journals, the public had other means of getting information: not only by different channels of information, but also through Viennese journals, and – judging by the sources in these news articles – German or French press and news agencies. Given the focus of the present study, we do not wish to discuss anything other than the influence of British media.

Secondly, the paper is centred around the greater issue of public pressure on foreign policy decision-making, therefore this paper applies Foreign Policy Analysis, which introduces media, interest groups and *public opinion* as independent factors in the process of policymaking.¹⁵ But what is public opinion? According to David L. Weakliem, the terminology appeared as early as the eighteenth century, but was first coined by Lord Russel in 1823: “it is fashion to point out increased and increasing influence of public opinion [...]”¹⁶ A more accurate account in Weakliem’s work is cited from Plamenatz,¹⁷ who states that public opinion is not necessarily

¹⁵ Marijke Breuning, *Foreign Policy Analysis* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007), 54-64, 120-123.

¹⁶ Quoted in David L. Weakliem, *Public Opinion* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2020), 2.

¹⁷ John Plamenatz, ‘Public Opinion and Political Consciousness,’ *Political Studies* 29 (1975), 342-351.

the voice of the public, but rather the opinion outside governance and its hierarchy, yet close enough to it so that it can be acquired and have an indirect influence. Since the nineteenth century, with wider access to education, the public has become increasingly involved in politics and the media. The social disparity in this regard meant that while the elite, middle classes and certain groups could access newspapers and articulate their voice to a greater extent, other groups could mostly resort to resisting policies.¹⁸ There are different tools, such as the aforementioned *framing* and *priming* – the promotion of a certain topic – at the disposal of the political or media elite to determine and promote an agenda.¹⁹ The ground-breaking book of Walter Lippmann and the following debate concluded that public opinion appears as something not coherent, but rather volatile, and therefore cannot serve as a solid basis for policymaking.²⁰ Noam Chomsky and Edward S. Herman in their work dedicated to Lippmann argue that a so-called ‘propaganda model of communication’ is in effect. The authors claim that interpersonal relationships, ownership, advertising markets and license, the pre-selection of journalists and self-censorship all influence agenda-setting in favour of the elite. Meanwhile, the audience does not have the means to control the media, and in a centralised market, the propaganda model is more effective.²¹ This paper applies their thesis to theorise that the Hungarian public was largely influenced by the British political elite and the papers favouring the Tory Party. Although the aforementioned work mainly examines 20th-century cases and might raise some scepticism in the application of the theory in a nineteenth-century context, the work of Curran and Seaton referenced in the book also supports the thesis that monopoly ensured the control of the media

¹⁸ Weakliem, *Public opinion*, 2-4.

¹⁹ For further reference see: Patricia Moy, David Tewksbury, and Eike Mark Rinke, ‘Agenda-Setting, Priming, and Framing’, in *The International Encyclopaedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*, edited by Jensen, K. B., Rothenbuler, E. W, Pooley, J. D. and Craig, R. T (Malden: Wiley & Blackwell, 2016), 1-13.

²⁰ Walter Lippmann, *Public Opinion* (New Brunswick, London: Transaction Publishers, [1922] 1998).

²¹ Edward S. Herman and Noam Chomsky, *Az Egyetértés-gépezet. A tömegmédiák politikai gazdaságtana* (Budapest: L’Harmattan, 2011). 13-20, 54-58.

for the elite as early as the middle of the nineteenth century.²² The elite domesticated the radical press of the 1840s, and by the 1860s, giant media enterprises ruled the market, which was also closely tied to political parties. It is not surprising that liberal politicians of the Gladstone era regarded media as an explicit means to control the sentiments of the public.²³ The scope of the present study involves the analysis of Hungarian news outlets. Among them the paper focuses particularly on those journals which do not belong to the group of official papers, and therefore do not act as the official mouthpiece of the government (such as *Pester Lloyd*), but rather as the carriers of public opinion. These Hungarian outlets researched are the *Pesti Napló*, *Hon*, *Ellenőr*, *Egyetértés*, and their understudied impact on foreign policy, as similar research on their Cisleithanian counterparts were already conducted, and as we will see the freedom of expression differed compared to the case of Hungary.²⁴

The role of the Hungarian press in Austro-Hungarian decision-making

As the wielder of the prerogative powers and a former absolutist ruler, the Austrian Emperor had all the means to control foreign policy. However, Franz Joseph did not solely make his decisions as he had a range of advisors – the military circle – and trusted Andrassy to handle foreign affairs.²⁵ The Habsburgs in the nineteenth century became increasingly aware of the power of the press as the Fourth Estate.²⁶ After losing to the Prussians at Sadowa in the fateful

²² James Curran and Jean Seaton, *Power without Responsibility. The Press and Broadcasting in Britain* (London, New York: Taylor and Francis, 1997).

²³ Curran and Seaton, *Power Without Responsibility*, 22-25, 39.

²⁴ Horst Haselsteiner, 'Öffentliche Meinung oder Meinungspluralität. Zum Widerhall der Okkupation in der Deutschsprachigen Presse der Donaumonarchie,' in *Otpor austrougarskoj okupaciji 1878*, eds Milorad Ekmečić (Sarajevo: Godine u Bosni i Hercegovini: naučni skup, 1978), 220-224, also see the work of Zachar, *Az osztrák-német liberális Alkotmánypárt*, who used the articles of the Viennese journal *Neue Freie Presse* to explore the influence of the Constitutional Party (*Verfassungspartei*) of German liberals in the legislative system of the Monarchy.

²⁵ Péter Hanák: 'Magyarország az Osztrák–Magyar Monarchiában. Túlsúly vagy függőség?', *Századok* 5 (1971), 928–929; Heiszler, *Az osztrák katonai vezetés*, 10-25, Éva Somogyi, *Magyarok a bécsi hivatalnoki világban. A közös külügyminisztérium magyar tisztviselői* (Budapest: MTA Bölcsészettudományi Kutatóközpont, Történettudományi Intézet, 2017), 32-37.

²⁶ Ágnes Deák and Ágnes Tamás, *Sziszifuszok küzdelme. Kormányzat és sajtópolitika Magyarországon 1860–1875* (Pécs: Kronosz Kiadó, 2021), 525-527.

year of 1866²⁷, and ceding the Empire's Western mission of uniting the Germans, for the sake of the integrity of the empire, the decision-makers of the newly established Austro-Hungarian Monarchy simply could no longer ignore the opinion of the public. Although the press played a crucial role in the Austro-Hungarian compromise (1867), as a minister of the Empire, Andrassy was very quick to apply the methods of his predecessors: in the press relations department of his bureau, he employed several secret agents as well as writers and middlemen (e.g. Mór Ludassi, Lajos Dóczy) to assert control over the media. His opinion, however, was that "as long as he enjoyed the confidence of the Emperor and delegations he would not need the press."²⁸ There is evidence that the department tried to influence British outlets: there are payslips for articles appearing in the *Daily Telegraph* and *Times*, but there is no information to what extent it worked.²⁹

Taking into account the difficulties and the initial expenses of a fresh newspaper, the costs of publicity were high in Austria-Hungary. Beyond the deposit and the colportage fee, the publishing market was carved up by limited companies (Athenaeum and Franklin Társulat) which were closely tied to the political elite.³⁰ Therefore, the press followed the division of political parties until 1875, after which the split and fusion of the old Deák Party³¹ resulted in the birth of the Liberal Party, *Pester Lloyd* – the semi-official organ edited by Miksa Falk –, and organs of the Left Centre opposition had to reposition themselves. The new premier Kálmán Tisza's mouthpiece was the small, but increasingly successful paper, *Ellenőr*. The journal *Hon*

²⁷ To commemorate the war and its consequences to German history, the year 1866 is often called the fateful year, or *Schicksalsjahr* in German. For further reference see Adam Wandruszka, *Schicksalsjahr 1866* (Koblenz: Styria Verlag, 1966).

²⁸ Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 98.

²⁹ Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 114, 559.

³⁰ Géza Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó és újságírás története a kezdetektől a rendszerváltásig* (Budapest: Wolters Kluwer, 2016), 179–185, Deák and Tamás, *Sziszifuszok*, 90–99, 318–333.

³¹ The group of political elite loyal to their leader, Francis Deák (1803–1876), which favoured the Austro-Hungarian compromise and held key government positions in Hungary in the late 1860s and early 1870s.

– sometimes labelled as the ‘Hungarian version of the *Times*’ – remained close to the once critical governing party, as it was edited by the widely respected novelist/writer, Mór Jókai. While *Pesti Napló* – the original organ of the Deák Party – could keep liberal readers even after the fusion, *Pester Lloyd* remained an important source of foreign news, but it descended to the rank of official journals, therefore it falls out of the scope of the present study. Similar to the opposition mouthpiece *Egyetértés*, *Pesti Napló* could openly criticise the policy of the Monarchy. The former paper was most active in the years 1874–1878 and was the organ of the Centre-Left along with those of the former Hungarian Independence Party.³²

To further explain the scope of the research it is worth mentioning, why the research excluded the study of German-Austrian newspapers or the Viennese press. While in Cisleithania Austrian and Slavic press freedom was limited by the press laws of the absolutist era (the 1862 edicts), in Hungary, the laws of 1848 (Article XVIII) were enacted, and Hungary enjoyed a temporary era of press freedom of press.³³ Although it must be mentioned that the influence of media was limited by several factors. Only 6% of the population had the right to vote, while the share of literacy of the population had barely reached 40% by 1880.³⁴ Regardless of the constitutional boundaries of the Cisleithanian press, it is already claimed that the semi-official and rather liberal journals³⁵ tried to influence the foreign policy of the Empire. Their impact is well-documented in connection with Andrassy’s resignation, but their critique stemmed rather from the Eastern policy, than the adoption of foreign news sources. One if not the most significant among them was the organ of the German-liberals of the Constitutional Party, the *Neue Freie*

³² Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 201-204, 206-208.

³³ Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 180.

³⁴ László Katus, *A modern Magyarország születése. Magyarország története 1711–1914* (Pécs: Bocz Nyomdaipari Kft., 2012), 370, 519.

³⁵ Organs such as *Neue Freie Press*, *Morgenpost*, *Neues Wiener Journal*, *Neues Wiener Tagblatt*, *Wiener Allgemeine Zeitung*, *Die Presse*.

Presse, but Andrassy rather resigned over the wish of the Emperor and the objection of certain (liberal) political figureheads in the Cisleithanian government and delegations over his exposé concerning the occupation of Bosnia in 1879.³⁶ Hence, the focus lies on the examination of the earlier mentioned Hungarian papers, and not on the Cisleithanian press and political elite, which was mostly concerned over fiscal matters of the Bosnian occupation, months after our examined period.

British politics and press, 1875–1878

As British media outlets mirrored and magnetized domestic politics, a brief summary of British politics is necessary to understand the underlying divisions of newspapers and their standpoints. Politics in Britain in the 1870s were not only defined by the two great parties – the Conservative Party (the Tories) and the Liberal Party – but also by their leaders, Benjamin Disraeli (Lord Beaconsfield) and W. E. Gladstone. The ideas of these statesmen were greatly influenced by the decades of foreign policy under the Palmerston premiership which put the liberal-imperial policies to practice.³⁷ In 1876, upon defeating his rival, Gladstone, Disraeli became prime minister for a second time. After winning the Queen the title of Empress of India and earning her support (along with the title Earl of Lord Beaconsfield), he made his position exceptionally strong compared to his cabinet members. One of the victims of his growing power was his old political ally, Lord Derby. As a foreign secretary, he kept a diary and recorded his meetings with editors and other media figures.³⁸ Lord Derby was not the only minister who was removed from the government, as Disraeli shuffled his cabinet during the crisis. The Bulgarian atrocities

³⁶ Diószegi, *Bismarck és Andrassy*, 331-334; Horst Haselsteiner, 'Öffentliche Meinung oder Meinungspluralität. Zum Widerhall der Okkupation in der Deutschsprachigen Presse der Donaumonarchie', in *Otpor austrougarskoj okupaciji 1878*, ed. Milorad Ekmečić (Sarajevo: Godine u Bosni i Hercegovini: naučni skup, 1978), 220-233.

³⁷ Swartz, Marvin, *The Politics of British Foreign Policy in the era of Disraeli and Gladstone* (London: Macmillan, 1985), 12-23.

³⁸ Vincent, John, comp., *The Diaries of Edward Henry Stanley, 15th Earl of Derby (1826–1893). Between September 1869 and March 1878* (London: Offices of the Royal Historical Society, University College London, London, 1994).

voiced by the liberal opposition put the centre of attention on the Government and its treatment of its Ottoman ally; the controversies divided both public opinion and political parties.³⁹ By the summer of 1876, the Turkish frontier became increasingly important as Ottoman bashi-bazouk troops quenched the rebellious provinces and committed atrocities among civilians, and Serbia and Montenegro entered the war with Russian advisers in their ranks.⁴⁰ During the crisis, British ministers and other statesmen like Lord Salisbury and Lord Carnarvon were in favour of a Russian, Christian solution to the crisis. The differences lead to major shifts in the cabinet and both the Conservatives and the Liberal parties.⁴¹ As the Conservative government and cabinet had their divisions, the Liberals were split into camps of agitating ‘Gladstonian radicals’, and the more practical and commercial ‘pro-peace’ Whigs.⁴²

The bellicose media – and the Conservative Party supporting some papers with the help of Montague Corry⁴³, – incited anger as hundreds gathered in Hyde Park to protest. The expression ‘jingoists’ appeared during the last months of the crisis, denoting those who favoured Russophobic views and also those who backed heavy measures in foreign policy by supporting Lord Beaconsfield. Jingoism marked the polarization of the public, as Conservatives channelled anti-Russian sentiments to the working class under the banner of national interests.⁴⁴ On the topic of British public opinion, the early work of G. Carslake Thompson still provides a very detailed introduction to the media sphere of the era.⁴⁵ An outstanding paper was the *Daily*

³⁹ The Opposition and its leader, Gladstone have successfully campaigned with his pamphlet *The Bulgarian Horrors and the Question in the East in 1876* and in the Midlothian Campaign of 1879.

⁴⁰ Ković, *Disraeli*, 122.

⁴¹ In 1878 Salisbury replaced Derby, Hardy went to the House of Lords and F. A. Stanley (Derby’s brother) joined the cabinet as Secretary for War, and Hicks Beach had become Colonial Secretary after the resignation of Carnarvon (Swartz, *Politics*, 85).

⁴² Ković, *Disraeli*, 84; Swartz, *Politics*, 40-41, 74-75.

⁴³ The secretary of the prime minister, in office 1874–1880.

⁴⁴ Carslake George Thompson, *Public Opinion and Lord Beaconsfield 1875–1880*, vol I. (London: Macmillan and Co., 1886), 52-59.

⁴⁵ Although Thompson has sound observations, his categorisation is admittedly biased (Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 72-170).

Telegraph, which became the ‘Tory-Mahometan’ paper, but despite the label, it remained a popular outlet.⁴⁶ Newspapers either supported the peace argument (*Daily News*) or pursued sensation and the involvement of the public in the affair. The *Pall Mall Gazette (P.M.G.)*, the *Standard (alternatively London Evening Standard)*, *Spectator* and the *Globe* belonged to the latter group.⁴⁷ One of the most reliable and impartial newspapers was *The Times*. Despite that the manager, J. C. MacDonald admittedly sympathized with Russians, the owner, John Walter and editor J. T. Delane were not committed to leading an ‘anti-Turkish’ paper.⁴⁸

British pro-Turkish and anti-Russian sentiments in Hungarian outlets

After the outbreak of the Herzegovinian revolts in the summer of 1875, Hungarian outlets initially remained calm and featured British articles in the usual manner as they did ever since the early nineteenth century.⁴⁹ University students, however, became increasingly active, mostly in answering to the governing party abandoning its earlier vision of an independent Hungary.⁵⁰ In Britain, the majority of the British Press was pro-Ottoman, and pro-status quo in the very beginning. In August the *Spectator* and *Times* published pro-peace articles with some humanitarian arguments, very much inspired by Greek supporter Liberals such as Lord Russell.⁵¹ By September 17, the *Times* mentioned that there could be Russian involvement behind the uprisings.⁵² Other papers estimated the dangerous possibility of Turkey conceding territories to Russia.⁵³ By November 1, the *Daily News* took an anti-Turkish stance, but other British organs were appalled by Russian diplomatic manoeuvres which left the line of reform

⁴⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 435-440.

⁴⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 432; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 246, 250-254.

⁴⁸ Swartz, *Politics*, 40.

⁴⁹ András Döbör, *Sajtópolitika és politikai sajtó Magyarországon (1780–1840)* (Budapest: Gondolat Kiadó, 2018), 188-190.

⁵⁰ Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 81-82.

⁵¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 217-224, *Spectator*, August 21, 1875, 1, *Times*, “The Herzegovina,” August 21, 1875, 6.

⁵² *Times*, “Herzegovina,” September 17, 1875, 5.

⁵³ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 225-231.

in favour of armed intervention.⁵⁴ *Times* and *P.M.G.* warned about Russian intentions, and also some theories appeared in the *Times* that Austria was willing to occupy Turkish provinces.⁵⁵ Also later that month Disraeli held his Guildhall speech, which implied British involvement.⁵⁶

In Hungarian papers, the main organ of the opposition, *Egyetértés* was eager to feature pro-Turkish articles in the *Daily Telegraph* and the *Standard*.⁵⁷ The turning point however came much later in the autumn of the next year, when the Hungarian press started to feature a number of articles from the British conservative press in the heat of Gladstone's atrocity campaign.

In January 1876, as the Great Powers joined the Andrassy Note, *Pesti Napló* voiced the necessity of joint action of the Three Emperors for a peaceful solution, while other papers deterred from pacifism. The opposition adopted a Russophobe view, but would not press the matter, as the government paper, *Ellenőr* in its February 15 issue called out Russia as the perpetrator behind the events in the Balkans.⁵⁸ At the same time, British outlets were mostly proposing peace: *Times* and *Daily Telegraph* emphasised how Britain was in favour of all points of the Austrian proposal.⁵⁹ Concerning the Hungarian papers, *Hon* published statements of English MPs and referenced the *Times* on Andrassy's reform plans.⁶⁰ At the end of the articles, general references were made to England's disposition to war. Although England was criticised in the paper, it was presented as Andrassy's partner in a possible 'eastern action'.⁶¹ In Britain by March, both liberal and conservative organs of the British Press stated that the Andrassy Note

⁵⁴ *Daily News*, November 1, 1875.

⁵⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 231-233, 243-255; *Times*, "Pan-Sclavonia," October 20, 1875, 4; *Times*, "Turkey," November 5, 1875, 5; *Times*, "The Eastern Question," December 1, 1875, 5; *P.M.G.*, "The European Prospect today," November 9, 1875, 1.

⁵⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 235-236.

⁵⁷ *Egyetértés* issues October 13-15, 1875 and December 29, 1875, 1-4.

⁵⁸ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 48.

⁵⁹ *Times*, "Count Andrassy's Note," January 27, 1876, 5. *Daily Telegraph*, January 17, 1876, 4.

⁶⁰ *Times*, "Count Andrassy's Note," January 20, 1876, 9.

⁶¹ *Hon*, January 24, 1876, 1.

has failed.⁶² British organs at the time were very dismayed by Austrian diplomacy and approved the rejection of the note by the British government. The Berlin Memorandum was even denounced as “[...] Austrian in principle, Russian in detail”⁶³ in the *Times*, and by June it went as far as to announce Britain as the only leading power to resolve the conflict.⁶⁴ Hungarian readers, however, could only read a filtered, different attitude in the papers. Therefore, the rejection of the note was portrayed as a call for an alliance. In its June 2 issue, the *Hon* considered the chances of British intervention and cited the *Observer* as it contrasted Britain with Russia. Also in the June 6 and 9 issues, it wrote on the new political direction of England and the Monarchy, and with the new Turkish ruler's accession to the throne a possible decisive action: “[...] but the fact is that it is in England's interest to isolate Russia [...] the fact is also that with an Eastern policy conducted in the English spirit the interests of our Monarchy are more certainly safeguarded [...]”⁶⁵ Further in June, the paper featured Disraeli's speeches. In the July 19 issue, the *Pesti Napló* also contemplated the chances of war and it was sceptical about the prospect of a settlement.⁶⁶

Starting from early June to September, *Times* published a great number of articles on the Bulgarian atrocities and set the agenda for all papers in the coming months.⁶⁷ In its June 9 issue, the *Hon* cited the *Times* and other London news sources.⁶⁸ In its June 30 issue, the *Hon* did a special feature on the Eastern Question and reports of British arms shipments, while also providing the readers with a multi-episode historical essay on the topic.⁶⁹ In the June issues of

⁶² Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I. 278-280; *Times*, “Invasion of Bosnia,” April 18, 1876, 7; *P.M.G.*, “The Eastern Question,” April 17, 1876, 1.

⁶³ *Times*, “The Berlin Conference,” May 23, 1876, 9.

⁶⁴ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 289.

⁶⁵ *Hon*, June 6, 1876, 1.

⁶⁶ Menyhárt, ‘A három császár’, 49-50.

⁶⁷ *Times*, “Atrocities in Bulgaria,” August 8, 1876, 5; *Times*, “Turkish Atrocities,” September 6, 1876, 8.

⁶⁸ *Hon*, June 9, 1876, 1; *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” June 9, 1876, 9.

⁶⁹ *Hon*, June 30, 1876, 1.

Ellenőr, the paper speculated a British involvement in a war against Russia and carried reports from English and 'warmongering' German newspapers.⁷⁰ *Pesti Napló* wrote about the infiltration of pan-Slavism into European public opinion, which it attributed to the Russian ties with the Monarchy.⁷¹ It was the point when the rumours of the May atrocities began to sink into the Hungarian press with a few weeks of delay. In Britain, *P.M.G.* suggested that 'humanitarians mislead' since they misjudged the actions of Turkey which sought integrity.⁷² Meanwhile, the *Daily News* criticised Disraeli and the Government and went on the offensive in its June 23 and July 8 issues.⁷³ To avoid damage, Derby communicated to the Constantinople ambassador, that he should do all in his power to stop the Porte and the possible outrage – *Daily News* and *Times* published Derby's despatch and later admired it.⁷⁴ These Blue Books were published in the *Times*, but the papers condemned the slaughter and portrayed Disraeli and Derby as responsible.⁷⁵ *Daily Telegraph* and *P.M.G.* started to build a narrative against the humanitarians to protect Derby's policy.⁷⁶

In the following months the pressure mounted on Andrassy, and the *Egyetértés* regained its pro-Turkish stance. The newspaper began to emphasise a narrative that Germany would certainly support the Hungarians in the event of a Russian-Hungarian conflict.⁷⁷ From the autumn of 1876 onwards, *Ellenőr* devoted a special 'Eastern War' column to the reports of the British and German news agencies, and during Andrassy's visit to Budapest, it published a particularly large number of articles on the topic of war. In its issue of September 7, 1876, it reported on the

⁷⁰ *Ellenőr*, June 1-2, 7-9, 19, 23 issues, 1876.

⁷¹ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 50-51.

⁷² Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 293-294.

⁷³ *Daily News*, June 23, 1876, 5; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 310-313.

⁷⁴ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 342-344; *Daily News*, August 12, 1876, 5.

⁷⁵ *Times*, "The Affairs of Turkey," July 22, 1876, 10; Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 316-317.

⁷⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I., 303-305, 336-337; *Daily Telegraph*, June 30, 1876; *P.M.G.*, "The Policy of the Government in the East," June 24, 1876, 1; *Daily Telegraph*, July 18, 1876, 4-5.

⁷⁷ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 52, 60.

change in English public opinion following the atrocities agitation “In England, agitation against Turkish atrocities is on the rise”).⁷⁸ In its September 10 issue, the paper goes as far as to call the agitation “philanthropy and Russophile rumble degraded to party manoeuvres.”⁷⁹ The same issue concluded its foreign affairs column with reviews of Gladstone's pamphlet in the *Morning Post*, *Daily Telegraph* and *Standard*.⁸⁰ In their quest for readership, the editors published a certain Mr H. Brown's anxious letters to Hungarians on the front page, which commented on Gladstone's protests, and at the same time discussed Hungarian policy, public opinion, and a desirable Turkish victory.⁸¹ The *Pesti Napló* also featured the events of the Serbian-Turkish war on the front page, but in its September 11 issue, it also presented Gladstone's speeches.⁸² On September 15, the *Daily Telegraph's* comment on ‘sickening humanitarianism’ was also featured in translation.⁸³ The mentions of Austrian-British cooperation continued in both countries’ media. In the September 29 issue, the *Times* commented on the atrocities and also claimed that if Austria was unwilling, it is up to Britain to keep order in the Balkans.⁸⁴ Also some anti-Russian sentiments – an article by the Bishop of Exeter – appeared in the *Times* by mid-September but the only paper was still *Daily Telegraph* which vehemently defended the government's position.⁸⁵ The turning point however seems to be the Aylesbury speech (September 20) of Disraeli. This is the speech that has most likely connected the anti-Russian feelings of Hungarian newsreaders and the pro-Turkish sentiments of the British conservative media.⁸⁶ The *Daily News* and the *Spectator* considered it catastrophic, while the *Times* generally approved it. The speech surprisingly revived the pro-

⁷⁸ *Ellenőr*, issues September 7, 1876, and October 13, 1876.

⁷⁹ *Ellenőr*, September 10, 1876, 1.

⁸⁰ *Ellenőr*, September 10, 1876, 1.

⁸¹ *Ellenőr*, issues September 11-24, 1876.

⁸² *Pesti Napló*, September 11, 1876, 1.

⁸³ *Pesti Napló*, September 15, 1876, 1.

⁸⁴ *Times*, “Eastern Question,” September 29, 1876, 4.

⁸⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. I.: 413, 432-435.

⁸⁶ *Egyetértés* welcomed and featured Disraeli's speech in a long lead in its September 25, 1876 issue (1-4).

Turkish voices in the country and discouraged the liberal camp.⁸⁷ In early October, Derby was outlined as a competent leader by the *Daily Telegraph* and *P.M.G.*. The papers tried to sell his idea, a modified memorandum called the ‘English Terms’, and also claimed that humanitarian attitude is the path of “national destruction”.⁸⁸ The *Times* criticised Derby but mentioned Austria and her possible move to occupy Bosnia in accordance with Russia.⁸⁹ Articles of both sides of the argument appeared in these papers, as Gladstone’s agitation continued throughout the month.⁹⁰ While *Daily News* and *Times* rekindled the humanitarian agitation, the *Spectator* in its October 21 issue wrote on how Austria seems inclined to join Russia in sharing the spoils: the only thing preventing them was the agitation.⁹¹ The Aylesbury speech also inspired *Egyetértés*, which blamed Gladstone and humanitarians for a pro-Russian attitude. The paper could identify more with Conservative goals, and therefore cited the *Daily Telegraph*.⁹²

In late October, *Pesti Napló* competed with the pro-government Viennese press in reporting news about a possible British or German alliance and criticised the *Times* for endorsing the pro-Russian demonstrations in Britain.⁹³ On October 9, *Times* disclosed a lengthy speech from W. E. Forster. In the speech the inaction of Austria is mentioned: “We cannot expect Hungary or Austria or any subject of the Austrian Empire, quietly to submit to Russia taking possession of the Lower Danube.”⁹⁴ *Ellenőr* adopted these tones of the English press, and in the later issues it quoted articles from the *Times*, *Telegraph* and German press, and despite being a government

⁸⁷ Carslake George Thompson, *Public Opinion and Lord Beaconsfield 1875–1880*, vol. II. (London: Macmillan and Co., 1886), 19–39; *Daily News*, September 21, 1876, 5; *Spectator*, September 23, 1876, 1; *Times*, “Mr. Gladstone and the Party,” September 26, 1876, 8.

⁸⁸ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 50–67, 77; *Daily Telegraph*, “The Bulgarian Massacres,” October 7, 1876, 5; *P.M.G.*, “The Porte and the English Proposals,” October 3, 1876, 9.

⁸⁹ *Times*, “Russia and Austria,” October 3, 1876, 8.

⁹⁰ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 71–81.

⁹¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 83; *Spectator*, October 21, 1876, 1.

⁹² *Egyetértés*, September 10, 11, 14, 19, 20 issues, 1876.

⁹³ *Pesti Napló*, October 20, 1876, 1.

⁹⁴ *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” October 9, 1876, 10.

paper, also criticised Hungarian inaction.⁹⁵ In its October 22 issue, the paper featured an article where students called for action:

To the students of the two universities [of Budapest]! The public of the nation has chosen. Hungarians cannot remain indebted to their Turkish neighbours. The progress and freedom of Europe are threatened by a disaster; the horror of the Siberian lead mines, the perpetrator of the Warsaw atrocities is trampling international rights, under the guise of the "bloody cross", while threatening the tranquillity of Europe and its protector, Hungary. [...] Let us show that the brotherly Turkish nation is accompanied in its bloody struggles by the sympathy of the Hungarian youth. [...] To express our sympathy for the Turkish nation, we will organize a torchlight procession [...].⁹⁶

On 21 October and the large gathering of individuals was reported in great detail in all of the Hungarian press. After the rally, a delegation of 18 people visited the Hungarian premier who – although he would not ban it – asked the students to postpone the march.⁹⁷ A reflection on the British press coverage can be seen in the Prime Minister's words to the students: “If you follow closely the foreign press, you must know, that the Hungarian nation will be placed in front of the world [...] as one which wishes to oppress the Eastern Christians, and therefore people like Gladstone may utter that the Hungarian race must be swept from the face of the Earth [...]”.⁹⁸ Overnight, the demonstrators became a mixed crowd of the bourgeoisie and workers of Budapest. Escorted by the police, they made their way to the house of the editor of *Hon*, Jókai, who, although had the intention of appeasing the protesters, did not join them.⁹⁹ Later, the crowd split and a small number of them marched to the Turkish consul's apartment, where they were dispersed by the police.¹⁰⁰ Later, students wanted to publish their proclamations in the ‘foreign press’, and in the October 28 issue of *Egyetértés*, *Times* and *Spectator* articles were also featured supporting the idea of dishonest Russian diplomacy. In these late October issues,

⁹⁵ *Ellenőr*, October 17, 1876, 1.

⁹⁶ *Ellenőr*, October 22, 1876, 1.

⁹⁷ Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 84.

⁹⁸ *Pesti Napló*, October 23, 1876, 1; *Egyetértés* October 24, 1876, 1-4.

⁹⁹ Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 86–87.

¹⁰⁰ *Ellenőr*, October 27, 1876, 1.

the paper also claimed that Andrassy was now in a difficult position as the *Reichsrat* considered limiting the powers of the ministry.¹⁰¹ Later in November the *Standard* also reinforced these notions.¹⁰² Although the paper for a short period was preoccupied with the publication of Lajos Kossuth's ideas on the Eastern Question and the necessity of a preventive war¹⁰³, the paper also wanted to make the audience believe in British participation. "England is prepared [...] and will fight until justice shall be done [...]"¹⁰⁴ Also around the same time, Beaconsfield addressed his Guildhall speech (November 9) to the audience of the Lord Mayor's banquet, shortly after the Tsar addressed his Moscow speech to his subjects. The tory press and the *Standard* connected the two speeches, and interpreted them as a hostile dialogue between the British premier and the Russian Tsar.¹⁰⁵ *Egyetértés* also featured the speech in full length in its November 14 issue.¹⁰⁶ Starting from mid-November, the bellicose party in England was on the rise. The *Daily News* remained critical of Beaconsfield and added that he would never convince Austria to go against Russia, but also admitted that the speech of the Tsar was a break with Derby's peaceful efforts.¹⁰⁷ These notions along with others were also featured in *Hon.*¹⁰⁸ *Egyetértés* and *Hon* started to cite the information gathered by *P.M.G.* and *Daily Telegraph* on Russian troops.¹⁰⁹ In the next year, from February until May 1877 the British public calmed down, and resorted to an observant mode throughout the conference period, as the readers were apparently more interested in diplomacy.¹¹⁰

¹⁰¹ *Egyetértés* issues October 26-31, 1876; *Times*, "The Eastern Question," October 21, 1876, 5; *Times*, "The Crisis," October 21, 1876, 9.

¹⁰² *Egyetértés* issues November 4, 7, 1876; *Standard*, "Count Andrassy," November 10, 1876, 5.

¹⁰³ *Egyetértés* issues November 5, 11, 25, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁴ *Egyetértés* November 11, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁵ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 93-107; also the lead article in *Standard*, November 10, 1876, 4.

¹⁰⁶ *Egyetértés*, November 14, 1876, 1-4.

¹⁰⁷ *Daily News*, November 25, 1876, 4.

¹⁰⁸ *Hon*, issues November 11, 14, 1876.

¹⁰⁹ *Egyetértés*, November 19, 1876, 1-4; *Hon*, November 26, 1876, 1; *P.M.G.*, "The Situation in Europe," November 17, 1876, 5.

¹¹⁰ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 128, 142-165.

In Hungary, from the end of 1876 onwards, part of the governing party, the opposition, and their press, associated Austro-Hungarian foreign policy failures with a dangerous Russian alliance. In the Hungarian parliament, MPs, like Lajos Mocsáry and Ignác Helfy denounced Tisza's illegal police orders in their interpellations and Beaconsfield's speech was used against the prime minister during a debate.¹¹¹ During the Spring of 1877, the students collected a great sum of donations and had a ceremonial sword made for Abdul Kerim, which they took to Constantinople, representing the goodwill of the Hungarian people in a semi-official capacity.¹¹² To deter this political fiasco, Tisza asked Andrassy in a lengthy letter to dissuade the students.¹¹³ The Hungarian premier however also successfully persuaded the Emperor to not apply stricter measures against the returning students as it would have an adversary effect on stability.¹¹⁴

During the Conference of Constantinople (December 23, 1876 – January 20, 1877), the *Daily Telegraph* committed itself to comment on Salisbury's mission and almost to instruct the British envoy, while also deeming Turkish reforms as the sufficient means to oppose Russia.¹¹⁵ In their February issues *Pesti Napló*, *Ellenőr* and *Egyetértés* featured the speeches of British conservatives and transcripts from the House of Commons.¹¹⁶ After the Russo-Turkish War broke out on April 24, 1877, the *Daily Telegraph* claimed that the Russian aim was to occupy the capital and therefore violate European and British interests.¹¹⁷ With British and Austrian interests aligning, on May 5 a full article was written in the *Times* on Austrian neutrality.¹¹⁸ Also a few days later, letters of a certain 'Anglophil' were published in the *Daily Telegraph*

¹¹¹ *Egyetértés*, November 26, 1876, 1-4.

¹¹² Sándor, *Tömegmegmozdulások*, 92-93.

¹¹³ HU-MNL, X, PA X689, 1794, 103. Kálmán Tisza to Gyula Andrassy, January 3, 1877.

¹¹⁴ HU-MNL-OL-P 4-(592), Kálmán Tisza to Emperor Franz Joseph, August 22, 1877.

¹¹⁵ *The Daily Telegraph*, January 6, 1877, 4-5.

¹¹⁶ *Egyetértés*, issues February 17, 18, 20, 1877, 1-4; *Ellenőr*, February 18, 1877, 1-2.

¹¹⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 184-185; *The Daily Telegraph*, issues April 27-30, 1877, 4-5.

¹¹⁸ *Times*, "Austria," May 5, 1877, 7.

and advocated for Britain to join Austria and Turkey against the Russians.¹¹⁹ We do not know the author of the latter article, but this is the time when secret talks between Andrásy and Lord Beaconsfield began.¹²⁰ During these weeks, *Times* also published an unusually large number of articles on Austria.¹²¹ In the Hungarian press, these notions also appeared in May, and some Hungarian politicians even advocated for an immediate military alliance with Britain.¹²² Furthermore, the *Daily Telegraph* and *Spectator* believed that if Britain did not intervene, the fleet and the country would lose prestige.¹²³

Articles in the *Pesti Napló* and *Egyetértés* criticised the loss of sovereignty of Hungarian foreign policy. Tisza's speech on July 1 reassured his party, and then, relying on information from Andrásy, he claimed that the Monarchy would not rule out the partition of Turkish territories in the Balkans. The parliament was then dissolved before the dispute could escalate. *Pesti Napló* published articles until 1878 quoting statements by opposition MPs who portrayed a pro-Russian policy as 'unnatural' and 'a prison' for Hungarians. With the occupation of Bosnia being floated, the voice of the Hungarian press became threatening.¹²⁴ After the October 15 defeat of the Ottoman forces, liberal voices of *Daily News* also assumed a possible British military intervention if Russians were to overwhelm Constantinople.¹²⁵ Now the pro-Turkish pressure was mounting on the government. In early November, Disraeli reinforced his support of his bellicose voters and condemned Liberals.¹²⁶ *Egyetértés*, *Ellenőr*, and the rest of the Hungarian press relied on their own correspondents for a few months, but later the opposition paper

¹¹⁹ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 186; *The Daily Telegraph*, May 15, 1877, 5.

¹²⁰ István Diószegi, 'Andrásy und Disraeli im Sommer des Jahres 1877', *Studia Historica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 156 (1980), <http://real-eod.mtak.hu/10997/>, accessed August 02, 2022.

¹²¹ *Times* "The War" and "Austrian Neutrality" articles in issues May 16, and June 2, 5, 14, 21, 25, 29, 1877.

¹²² *Hon*, May 7, 1877, 1; *Egyetértés*, May 17, 1877, 1-4; *Ellenőr*, issues May 20-22, 1877.

¹²³ Thompson, *Public opinion* vol. II., 250-254; *The Daily Telegraph*, "British Troops for the East," July 25, 1877, 5; *Spectator*, August 18, 1877, 1.

¹²⁴ Menyhárt, 'A három császár', 52-60.

¹²⁵ *Daily News*, November 21, 1877, 5.

¹²⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 262-265.

admitted the Turkish defeat, while also referencing the *Daily Telegraph* to cover the issue.¹²⁷ It became clear that moderates like Derby were overwhelmed by the bellicose party. With the fall of Plevna on December 10, the pro-Turkish media were of the opinion that conference and mediation is reasonable, but from mid-January 1878, war was also on the table.¹²⁸ *Egyetértés* featured a variety of articles from the *Times*, *Daily Telegraph*, and *Morning Post* and also saw mediation as fitting.¹²⁹ Later the paper called out *Times* as an opposition mouthpiece, one which supports “the bloodthirsty philanthropists”.¹³⁰ In its December 26 issue, the *Times* alluded that the British government was ready for war and turned to the policy of armed neutrality. In early January, the *Daily News* also communicated the notion, that at some point England ‘must’ join the war on their side.¹³¹ The *Standard* reinforced the idea, while the *Globe* (December 19 issue) speculated that Russians would force Turkey to accept peace on their terms.¹³² Russophobe, pro-government working men’s associations came to the forefront, as even the Liberal Party itself became divided concerning the issue of the straits. British anti-Russian protesters met on December 29, in Trafalgar Square. As the event was announced by the *Times* issue of the same day, two days later, self-proclaimed “Turkish friends” in Hungary – mainly Hungarian opposition politicians, like Ignác Helfy and Lajos Simonyi – sent their ‘sympathetic greetings’ from Budapest via the *Times*.¹³³ Shortly after the exchange, *Egyetértés* featured news from *Times*, *P.M.G.*, *Daily News*, *Daily Telegraph* and *Standard* articles.¹³⁴ *Hon* also reported on the British domestic events with great excitement.¹³⁵ For a brief moment, it seemed that Britain was united under the banner of intervention, but on January 2, Lord Carnarvon’s speech

¹²⁷ See *Ellenőr*, issues October 16, 20, 1877; *Egyetértés*, November 19, 1877, 1-4; *The Daily Telegraph*, November 17, 1877, 5.

¹²⁸ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 266-267.

¹²⁹ *Egyetértés*, December 12, 1877, 1-4.

¹³⁰ *Egyetértés*, December 25, 1877. 1-4.

¹³¹ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 270-273; *Daily News*, issues January 2-3, 1878.

¹³² Lead article in *Standard*, December 20, 1877, 4,

¹³³ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 290-291.

¹³⁴ *Egyetértés*, December 31, 1877, 1-4; also a similar feature in the next issue January 1, 1877, 2-3.

¹³⁵ *Hon*, issues December 28–31, 1877.

dissuaded the jingoes.¹³⁶ After the first sitting of Parliament, Beaconsfield stated in his speech that there was no need for the Andrassy Note or the involvement of the Great Powers, as the English neutral stance was deliberate, and Britain would be able to defend its interests with or without allies.¹³⁷ This was also possibly a message for Andrassy, who, according to *Egyetértés* was now under heavy pressure from the Vienna circles as the *Pester Lloyd* officially took his side.¹³⁸ There were also *Times* articles in early January which suggested Austro-British cooperation.¹³⁹ *Egyetértés* published more articles on the possibility of Britain entering the conflict.¹⁴⁰ As the paper eagerly reported on the sailing of the British fleet near the conflict, it also criticised the inaction of Austria until the end of the month.¹⁴¹ The notion of alliance returns much later, after the one-sided preliminary peace efforts imposed by Russia on Turkey.¹⁴² Lastly, the alliance is mentioned by the *Times* before Britain and Austria secretly agreed on their terms of what policy to follow in the Balkans.¹⁴³

Conclusion – Political consequences in Austria–Hungary. The effect of British tory newspapers

Although there is no direct evidence to connect the Hungarian public and the opinions expressed in the press, as Hungarian newspapers adopted the articles of the British conservative press, unrest followed in the Dual Monarchy. This may have been due to the fact that the major Austrian and Hungarian news agencies were only established during the crisis, and papers of the Monarchy could rely only on agencies such as Havas, Reuters and Times, and to some extent articles in German/Viennese newspapers.¹⁴⁴ The editor of *Egyetértés* in the November

¹³⁶ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 294-295; *Daily News*, January 3, 1878, 3.

¹³⁷ Thompson, *Public opinion*, vol. II., 300-301.

¹³⁸ *Egyetértés*, January 3, 1878.

¹³⁹ *Times*, “Armistice Negotiations,” January 14-15, 1878, 5; *Times*, “The War and Peace Negotiations,” January 21, 1878, 9.

¹⁴⁰ *Egyetértés*, issues January 9-12, 1878.

¹⁴¹ *Egyetértés*, issues January 14, 17, 20, 1878.

¹⁴² *Times*, “The Eastern Question,” March 14, 1878, 9.

¹⁴³ *Times*, issues May 31, June 1-3, 1878, on the matter of the agreement see: William A. Gould, ‘The Anglo-Austrian Agreement of 1878’, *English Historical Review*, (1926), 108-112.

¹⁴⁴ Buzinkay, *A magyar sajtó*, 185-186.

11, 1875 issue even indicates that the English press had correspondents all over the Balkans, which Austro–Hungarian papers could afford only much later.¹⁴⁵ By adopting the British news of the crisis in the East, they also 'imported' the political narrative of British outlets and what was inspired by the Conservative Party elite. By fitting it to their anti-Russian view, the agenda was set for the press in both pro-government and opposition papers in Hungary. In line with Herman and Chomsky's concept, the idea that the adopted agenda shaped the 'position' of public opinion is consistent. Despite the fact that press support was an established tool to control the press in the Monarchy, Hungarian outlets departed considerably from the line that would have been comfortable for the decision-makers and caused a major political crisis. The aforementioned is most notable in the case of *Egyetértés* and its adoption of a bellicose narrative from *The Daily Telegraph*, but at some point during the crisis, both the opposition and the government press criticised the seemingly passive Austro-Hungarian foreign policy. Similar to the Midlothian campaign that led to the Liberal Party's victory in British politics, the Eastern Question had upset the 1878 elections in Hungary, and the Tisza regime was shaken when the party lost 100 seats in the legislature.¹⁴⁶ The pressure of the Hungarian public and attitude also had a direct effect when Andrassy and Tisza cast their vote in the January 14-15, 1878 Imperial War Council. The spectacular expressions of Hungarian public opinion were used in their arguments as they tried to justify the idea of a preventive war against Russia, instead of the occupation of Bosnia. In the end, Franz Joseph and the military circle advised Andrassy to rather prepare for the peace talks – later known as the Berlin Congress of 1878.¹⁴⁷

¹⁴⁵ *Egyetértés*, November 11, 1875.

¹⁴⁶ Katus, *A modern Magyarország születése*, 362-363.

¹⁴⁷ László Bencze, *Bosznia és Hercegovina okkupációja 1878-ban* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, 1987), 44-49.

In 1878, the Austro-Hungarian leadership and the influential military circles had to reckon with two consequences of the anti-Russian/pro-Turkish narrative in Hungarian public opinion. Firstly, public opposition in Cisleithania, which opposed the Monarchy's military action because of the expected costs. Secondly Andrassy, the former national hero – praised by Deák as the miraculous statesman – had earned the disapproval of the Hungarian public who, instead of a war in the East, faced the occupation of Bosnia, against the realm of the ‘brotherly’ Turkish people. A year later in 1879, Andrassy resigned, and in an undated document, he tells us that the press should not have judged him so harshly, because “a minister bears his only duty [...] to history itself. [...] If a minister lets things go their own way [...] both halves of the Monarchy are united in the joy that nothing really happens. And then the press and the delegates are perfectly content”.¹⁴⁸

¹⁴⁸ HU-MNL-OL-P 4-(592), Note 33.

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Diaspora Engagement and International Relations in the Cold War

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Abstract

In the last two decades, a growing number of studies attempted to incorporate diasporas and diasporic activities into the literature of International Relations. The need for incorporation arose seemingly in parallel with the increasing body of literature on diasporas, which stems from the proliferation of diaspora policies. This paper aims to add a historical perspective to the discussion by reviewing the diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic in the context of Soviet bloc states during the Cold War. The study examines the archival sources of Radio Free Europe to explore the state-diaspora relations of Soviet bloc countries in the international system.

The paper applies the inductive method of qualitative textual analysis to examine the documentation of Hungarian diaspora policies and analyse them along with the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian policies, as they were recorded by the respective units of Radio Free Europe. The study discusses a novel typology of diaspora engagement policies which is the outcome of the software-assisted qualitative analysis of the archival records. The study reflects on the state-diaspora nexus of the Soviet bloc countries and hence contributes to the literature on diaspora policies of authoritarian states.

Introduction

The study of diaspora engagement policies resulted in the emergence of various new typologies in the last few decades, owing to the numerous comprehensive researches conducted in the field. Previous studies presented comparative analyses between different categories of policies reflecting on the connection between diaspora policies and the political system of states that apply them, and on the role of diasporas in the international system. Even though earlier findings provide excellent insight into the diversity of diaspora policymaking, the literature predominantly discusses liberal democracies, thus, with a few exceptions¹⁴⁹, there is a lack of research on authoritarian states and their diasporas.

My paper speaks to this gap in the literature, and aims at explaining the diaspora policymaking processes of authoritarian states during the Cold War. My paper explores the archival records of Radio Free Europe (RFE) and argues how Radio Free Europe documented, interpreted and reflected on the state-diaspora nexus regarding the Hungarian People's Republic. The main research question is what diaspora engagement policies were recorded by the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe? The paper argues that in order to thoroughly understand the diaspora policies that a state applies, the policies have to be examined in their given political context. In the case of the Hungarian People's Republic, the context is the political system of the Soviet bloc, therefore, the paper analyses the diaspora policies of the Hungarian state along with the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian diaspora policies of the era.

My paper also argues that through inductive qualitative research, a typology of diaspora engagement policies can be developed to further analyse the attempts of the state to engage

¹⁴⁹ Notable exceptions include: Gerasimos Tsurapas, "Theorizing State-Diaspora Relations in the Middle East: Authoritarian Emigration States in Comparative Perspective," *Mediterranean Politics* 25, no. 2 (2020): 135–159; Gözde Böcü, "Home and Host Country Policy Interaction in the Making of Turkey's Diasporas," *Middle East Critique* 31, no. 4 (2022): 355-370; Gözde Böcü and Bahar Baser, "Transnational Mobilization of Future Generations by Non-Democratic Home States: Turkey's Diaspora Youth Between Empowerment and Co-optation," *Ethnopolitics* (2022).

with its diasporans. This research applies qualitative textual analysis: the coding of the primary archival sources and the thematic analysis were carried out using NVivo software. The primary sources of the research include the Subject Files and Information Items series of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe that are in the holdings of Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives in Budapest. The archival documents were digitised, and then through the method of thematic analysis, a typology of diaspora engagement policies was created by identifying the core elements of diaspora policymaking of the Hungarian People's Republic.

The empirical research findings discuss the novel typology of diaspora engagement policies that I created on the basis of archival source analysis. The typology differentiates ten major categories of diaspora policies: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies. The categories and subcategories of diaspora policies provide an insight into how employees of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe perceived the state-diaspora relations. The paper explains to what extent the typology that emerged as a result of the qualitative analysis can provide a better understanding of diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War.

Theoretical underpinnings

In order to establish a sound theoretical foundation for the discussion, it is crucial to review the underlying literature in the field of diaspora policies. Since the premise of the present study is the analysis of primary sources, it is worth reviewing how the literature on diaspora studies can contribute to source analysis. As political scientist Francesco Ragazzi argues: "Identifying the characteristic features of diaspora policies is key to assessing the ability of explanatory frameworks to account for these characteristics and their regularities."¹⁵⁰ Ragazzi's argument

¹⁵⁰ Francesco Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis of Diaspora Policies," *Political Geography* 41, (July 2014): 76.

gives a short, but thorough rationale for this paper, since this study aims at identifying the aspects of diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic by conducting a thematic analysis of archival documents. The goal of thematic coding is to construct the concepts that define the individual diaspora policies and hence contribute to the development of an explanatory typology.

Considering modern diaspora studies, researchers from the fields of geography, international relations, sociology and ethnology have already developed distinct theoretical frameworks to analyse modern migration processes, diasporic activities, and diaspora policies. However, the historical application of these theoretical frameworks would be anachronistic considering the Cold War period, due to the fact that conceptual frameworks that form the basis of modern diaspora policies and their typologies primarily describe liberal democracies, rather than authoritarian states. Given the above-mentioned critical thought, it should be noted that already existing frameworks can be helpful and highly practical in coding and developing a genuine theoretical framework. Though it may seem contradictory to the previous statement about anachronism, the review of modern typologies can be helpful since it reflects the process of analysing diaspora policies and creating explanatory frameworks.

In his 2014 article, Ragazzi differentiates three distinct but interconnected frameworks of diaspora policies: the structural-instrumental framework, the ethnic conception hypothesis and the governmentality framework. The structural-instrumental framework argues that states behave in accordance with their position at either the core or the periphery of the world economy.¹⁵¹ The ethnic conception hypothesis claims that a diaspora policy of a state is a response to the challenges of globalisation.¹⁵² Ragazzi argues that, though the structural-

¹⁵¹ Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis," 82.

¹⁵² Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis," 82.

instrumental framework and the ethnic conception hypothesis give an insight into the factors that determine diaspora policies, taking only material factors or ethnic conceptions of citizenship into consideration cannot lead to a thorough framework for analysing diaspora policies.¹⁵³ He therefore suggests the governmentality framework. According to his definition of the concept: “diaspora policies are shaped by modifications in programs of government and practices of power,” later adding “governmentality assumes a strong link between the types of political-economic rationalities and regimes (planned economy, welfare state, neo-liberal state) and diaspora policies.”¹⁵⁴ As Ragazzi argues, the governmentality framework gives a broader political-economic context for analysing state interests and diaspora policies.¹⁵⁵

Considering governmentality, geographer and migration scholar Alan Gamlen goes further than Ragazzi by presenting a typology of diaspora engagement policies within the governmentality framework. Gamlen argues that there are three types of diaspora engagement policies: capacity building policies, extending rights to the diaspora, and extracting obligations from the diaspora.¹⁵⁶ Within these higher-level policies, Gamlen differentiates subareas of diaspora policies. Within capacity building policies, Gamlen distinguishes symbolic nation-building and institutional building policies; policies of extending rights include practices aiming at political incorporation and providing civil and social services to emigrants; finally, by extracting obligation Gamlen means investment policies and lobby promotions.¹⁵⁷

Peggy Levitt and Rafael de la Dehesa point out that diaspora policies reconfigure “the traditional understanding of sovereignty, nation and citizenship,”¹⁵⁸ while Gamlen argues that

¹⁵³ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 82-87.

¹⁵⁴ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 82.

¹⁵⁵ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 87.

¹⁵⁶ Alan J. Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement Policies: What are they and what kinds of states use them?,” *Working Paper* 32 (Oxford: University of Oxford, 2006), 5-6.

¹⁵⁷ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 6-18.

¹⁵⁸ Peggy Levitt and Rafael de la Dehesa, “Transnational Migration and the Redefinition of the State: Variations and Explanations,” *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 26, no. 4 (2003): 606.

“diaspora engagement policies (re)produce citizen-sovereign relationships with expatriates, thus transnationalizing governmentality.”¹⁵⁹ Thus, we can see that conducting diaspora policies means (re)gaining legitimate power over expatriates. Gamlen also highlights that such policies “cannot be seen as singular, discrete, or historically *sui generis*. Rather, they form a constellation of institutional and legislative arrangements and programmes that come into being at different times, for different reasons, and operate across different timescales at different levels within the state.”¹⁶⁰ Therefore, taking a wider time frame, such as the Cold War, provides space for problematising the dimension of time within the typology of diaspora engagement policies, since it can allow for deeper analysis, and in this way, it is possible to explore not only which policies were created, but also the whys and hows of diaspora policymaking. A wider time frame can also help understand the transformation of the institutional system of diaspora policies.

As political theorist Szabolcs Pogonyi argues, one of the variables of diaspora policies that one should consider is agency.¹⁶¹ Pogonyi quotes Stéphane Dufoix saying that considering diaspora as the initiator of engagement policies reflects on the various conflicting interests of heterogeneous diasporas.¹⁶² Anthropologist Michel S. Laguerre also points out in his 1998 publication that “the diaspora can be seen as a political agency.”¹⁶³ This political agency acts in a transnational political field, which is, according to Laguerre, “an open arena in which elected and non-elected individuals, with or without the explicit knowledge of the state – and sometimes acting against official state policies – engage formal and informal political practices

¹⁵⁹ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 4-5.

¹⁶⁰ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 20.

¹⁶¹ Pogonyi Szabolcs, “Transborder Kin-minority as Symbolic Resource in Hungary,” *Journal on Ethnopolitics and Minority Issues in Europe* 14, no. 3 (2015): 76.

¹⁶² Pogonyi, “Transborder Kin-minority,” 78.

¹⁶³ Michel S. Laguerre, *Diasporic Citizenship: Haitian Americans in Transnational America* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 1998), 157.

for the purpose of influencing the everyday policies and politics of another state.”¹⁶⁴ Considering the Cold War context, such a transnational political agency meant a threat to the Soviet bloc countries since it challenged the authority of the state. This thought is reflected in Sławomir Łukasiewicz’s work, who argues that emigration from a Soviet bloc country was considered as “an act of contestation against the political system,”¹⁶⁵ in other words a “mechanism for delegitimizing” the political authority of the sending state.¹⁶⁶

Yossi Shain argues that diasporas are capable of independent political actions;¹⁶⁷ moreover they can serve as “bearers for the ideals of recovery and restoration.”¹⁶⁸ From the perspective of a dictatorial regime, diasporas’ capacity for restoration can be understood as a delegitimising process against the leadership of the regime. Shain adds four concerns of diasporas that influence diasporic activities regarding conflict resolution: maintaining their ethnic identity, competition for leadership of the transnational community, organisational interest, and other political interests of diasporas.¹⁶⁹ These activities and interests are important from the point of view of the present study since diaspora policies do not necessarily appear explicitly in the primary sources, but as reactions to certain diasporic activities.

The theoretical background of this study is visibly interdisciplinary; however, there are core elements that greatly help the coding process of the primary sources. Firstly, Ragazzi’s argumentation draws attention to segments of the archival documents that reflect on the practices of the Hungarian state as a sovereign power, through which the state tried to extend its authority over the emigrant communities. Secondly, Gamlen’s typology and Levitt and

¹⁶⁴ Laguerre, *Diasporic Citizenship*, 158.

¹⁶⁵ Sławomir Łukasiewicz, “The Polish Political System in Exile, 1945-1990,” *Polish American Studies* 72, no. 2 (Autumn 2015): 29.

¹⁶⁶ Łukasiewicz, “The Polish Political System,” 29.

¹⁶⁷ Yossi Shain, “The Role of Diasporas in Conflict Perpetuation or Resolution,” *SAIS Review* 12, no. 2 (2002): 116.

¹⁶⁸ Shain, “The Role of Diasporas,” 118.

¹⁶⁹ Shain, “The Role of Diasporas,” 128.

Dehesa's notion of sovereignty raises questions, such as: what institutional system served the policymaking process of the Hungarian state, what rights of émigrés were recognised by the state, and how the Hungarian state tried to exploit its émigrés. Lastly, Laguerre's, Łukasiewicz's, and Shain's works focus the coding process on diasporic activities that could evoke a response from the Hungarian state in the form of diaspora policies. This paper addresses issues which could contribute to the understanding of the relations between the Soviet bloc countries and their diasporic communities by further exploring the unique dynamics of the diaspora engagement policies of the era, which could help us to reveal the structural changes in the state-diaspora connections in the Soviet bloc.

Methodology and the Primary Sources

The method applied in the present research is a thematic analysis based on qualitative text coding. Qualitative text coding is a process which aims at analysing and organising textual data in order to find significant, generalizable patterns. Qualitative text coding divides the textual data into codes, categories or labels that are characteristic of a specific theme or phenomenon. Coding can help researchers to "establish a framework of thematic ideas" about the text.¹⁷⁰ I carried out the data-driven coding in NVivo, and then I condensed the emerging codes, categories, and themes into a typology of diaspora engagement policies, which, therefore, reflects the hierarchy of the coding tree.

As mentioned in the previous section, the theoretical literature on diaspora policies greatly helped the coding process by suggesting subquestions of the research. Apart from the main research question on the diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic, the research focused on the following subquestions: 1.) Through what practices did the Hungarian state try to engage with its émigrés? 2.) What institutional system served the diaspora

¹⁷⁰ Graham R. Gibbs, *Analyzing Qualitative Data* (London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2007), 38.

policymaking process of the Hungarian state? 3.) What rights of émigrés were recognised/denied by the state? 4.) What diasporic activities could evoke a response from the Hungarian state? These subquestions helped the research by constantly refocusing the coding process on data segments that are relevant to the study.

The primary sources of the research are archival records of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe. In order to contextualize the archival documents, it is worth discussing a few pieces of background information on the source material. Radio Free Europe (RFE) was established in 1949, with the aim of directing Western propaganda towards the Soviet satellite states.¹⁷¹ RFE broadcast uncensored radio programmes behind the Iron Curtain with the purpose of competing with the heavily censored local radio stations of Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Poland, Bulgaria, Albania, and Romania. Though Radio Free Europe tried to cover its ties to any Western governments, the radio was an instrument of US foreign policy.¹⁷²

In order to achieve Western propaganda goals, it was important that radio programmes broadcast reliable information. Therefore, RFE paid special attention to the collection and analysis of sources through the News and Information Service division. The division provided press monitoring transcripts, reports from Field Offices that were located all over Europe, background analyses, and research studies for the different broadcasting Units of RFE.¹⁷³ The most important documents from the archival records of RFE for the present research are the information items, which contain reports based on interviews conducted with the escapees in Western European countries. Today, these reports serve as primary sources on the political and economic systems of Soviet bloc countries, including reports on the policies through which the Hungarian state tried to engage with its émigré communities.

¹⁷¹ Robert Holt, *Radio Free Europe* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1958), 3.

¹⁷² Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 3-4.

¹⁷³ Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 98-109.

The coding and analysis of the relevant reports reveal what diaspora policies of the Hungarian state Radio Free Europe documented during the Cold War. It is crucial to note though that the primary sources reflect the viewpoint of RFE, therefore, the present study provides a meso-level analysis of diaspora engagement. Thus, the typology of diaspora policies, which is presented in the following section, sheds light on how Radio Free Europe perceived state-diaspora relations.

Documentation of Hungarian Diaspora Policies by Radio Free Europe

My analysis of the reports of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe led to the creation of ten categories of diaspora engagement policies, as it is summarised in *Table 1*: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies.

Control policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Controlling contact with émigrés ▪ Monitoring policies ▪ Harassment practices
Cultural policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing cultural institutions ▪ Organising conferences ▪ Organising summer universities ▪ Organising other cultural activities
Institutional building policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing consulate services ▪ Establishing ministerial-level agencies ▪ Maintaining World Federation of Hungarians
Investment policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic policies ▪ Knowledge remittance policies
Mobility policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Issuing passports ▪ Issuing visas ▪ Denying re-entry to home state ▪ Restricting exit and transit policies
Political incorporation policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Citizenship policies ▪ Sanctioning policies ▪ Granting amnesty
Propaganda policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Broadcasting “Homeland” radio program ▪ Press ▪ Communicating with émigrés
Redefection policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extending appeals towards émigrés ▪ Contacting émigrés

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing institutional background for the redefection campaign
Social policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organising social activities ▪ Providing free-of-charge dispensary ▪ Establishing pensioner homes for elderly returnees
Symbolic policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organising diaspora conferences ▪ Organising meetings with high-ranked state representatives

Table 1

The first type of policies to discuss is control policies. This category emerged from the segments that described situations or reported on events in which Hungarian authorities tried to level a certain degree of state control over either citizens who had connections with émigrés, or over visiting and returning émigrés. Control policies consist of three subcategories, as *Table 1* shows, namely controlling contact with émigrés, monitoring practices, and harassment practices.

Controlling any kind of contact with émigrés abroad manifested in actions such as forcing citizens to write letters to their émigré relatives to inform them about policies introduced in their home state,¹⁷⁴ or to inform them that Hungarian authorities were aware of their political activities.¹⁷⁵ Authorities also tried to force citizens who visited Western countries to contact émigrés and obtain information from them.¹⁷⁶ Controlling contact with émigrés also meant, in some cases, the restriction of communication in order to stop the flow of information in both directions.¹⁷⁷

Monitoring practices describe both the surveillance of communication with émigrés¹⁷⁸ and of relatives of émigrés residing in Hungary.¹⁷⁹ Harassment practices were carried out within the

¹⁷⁴ “Restrictions on passports issuance” 12 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁵ “Atmosphere of distrust and suspicion growing against relatives of defectors” 19 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁶ “Hungarian authorities’ interest in refugees’ reaction to consular passport” 27 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁷⁷ “The regime’s attitude towards Hungarians living abroad” 19 January 1968. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁸ “Persons having contact with refugees being checked” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁹ “Censorship – foreign currency offenses” 19 December 1967. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/3.

border of the state, however, they affected émigrés who visited the countries. Reports reveal cases according to which visiting émigrés were harassed by Hungarian authorities, in some cases their visas were confiscated,¹⁸⁰ and in several other cases visiting émigrés were threatened up to the point when they finally “voluntarily” gave up their intention to leave the country again.¹⁸¹

The second type of diaspora engagement policies is cultural policies. Within this category, as *Table 1* presents, there are four subcategories, namely establishing cultural institutions, organising conferences, summer universities, and other cultural activities. While summer universities predominantly aimed at promoting Hungarian language learning, scientific conferences dealt with a wide range of topics, hence, the two subcategories are labelled separately. Other cultural activities include cultural evenings and commemoration of historical events organised by the Hungarian legation. As can be seen, policies concerning cultural activities were much less varied than the above-mentioned control policies.

Reports on the establishment of cultural institutions predominantly deal with the Hungarian Houses that were established in several Western countries. These cultural institutions were state founded and often used to provide a platform for the dissemination of state propaganda.¹⁸² Apart from state-funded institutions, much emphasis was put on engaging with the diaspora through cultural ties, such as language learning. Since 1970, the World Association of Hungarians had organised conferences in order to discuss the status of the Hungarian Language in the diaspora and to arrange training for teachers of the Hungarian language.¹⁸³ The Mother Tongue conference soon became one of the most successful projects of the state-controlled World Association of Hungarians. Language learning opportunities were offered through summer

¹⁸⁰ “Emigrant visiting Hungary prevented from returning to US” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/10.

¹⁸¹ “Former Hungarian citizen visitors detained in Hungary” 26 October 1963. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁸² “Current activity of the regime-sponsored Hungarian House in Paris” 29 March 1962. HU OSA 300-40-4:2/18.

¹⁸³ “Hungarians abroad should learn Hungarian” 14 August 1970. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/4.

universities and summer camps,¹⁸⁴ which also provided an opportunity to build up the reputation of Hungary among diasporans.

The third category of diaspora policies is institutional building policies. In this category, institutions do not cover cultural institutions, but consulate services and ministerial-level agencies. *Table 1* shows the different layers of this policy. As the coding process revealed, consulate services served the purpose of providing information for émigrés, especially about redefection possibilities,¹⁸⁵ and also providing diplomatic and passport services, besides monitoring émigrés and their connection with the home state and the recipient country.¹⁸⁶ Two key institutions were repeatedly discussed in the reports, the Independent Agency of Hungarians Abroad and the World Federation of Hungarians (sometimes mentioned as World Associations of Hungarians), which served the purpose of engaging with diasporas and influencing their organisations.¹⁸⁷

During the coding process, as *Table 1* shows, two major types of investment policies were detected: economic policies and knowledge remittance policies. The concept of knowledge remittance reflects on the activities of the state through which diasporans were encouraged to engage in scientific networks with their homeland, such as networking opportunities provided by scientific conferences.¹⁸⁸ Interestingly, all the reports discussing scientific connections, originate in the late 1980s, or at least no earlier attempts were recorded by RFE.

Economic policies predominantly relied on émigrés' foreign contacts and their financial capacity and they aimed at increasing the inflow of hard currency to Hungary.¹⁸⁹ Confiscating

¹⁸⁴ "Courses for young Hungarians living abroad" 17 July 1975. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/4.

¹⁸⁵ "Announcement by the Hungarian legation in London on the amnesty" 11 July 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/22.

¹⁸⁶ "Recent Aspects of Redefection Campaign" 16 January 1956. HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

¹⁸⁷ "Hungarian government's link with Hungarians abroad" 13 August 1986. HU OSA 300-40-2:22/3.

¹⁸⁸ "East European Governments' Attitude," HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2.

¹⁸⁹ "Situation concerning foreign currency" 22 November 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:19/3.

émigrés' properties that were left behind when they left the country was another attempt to increase income, especially in the case of confiscated flats that were later re-sold.¹⁹⁰

The fifth category of diaspora engagement policies is mobility policies. Policies included in this category are in connection with the issuance of passports and visas, or restriction on the movement of citizens. As *Table 1* presents, records of Radio Free Europe focused on four types of travel documents: consular passports,¹⁹¹ re-entry visas, visitor visas and exit visas.¹⁹² Since the process of issuing travel documents and refusal of issuance were discussed in separate reports of RFE, different subcategories were developed to represent them.

Refusal of the issuance of travel documents was justified by authorities on the pretext of political activities against the Hungarian state or of the actions of emigrant relatives.¹⁹³ Denial of re-entry was justified by a quite loose description of activities: “persons who have given away state secrets, defamed the Hungarian social order, have contacted hostile organisations or have caused any other harm to the country, will be refused permissions for returning home.”¹⁹⁴ Considering the fact that émigré organisations which were not under the control of the Hungarian state were believed to be hostile, the above-mentioned justification could be used whenever it was in the interest of the authorities.

Table 1 also introduces the category of political incorporation policies. Political incorporation is understood as a set of policies aimed at engaging and integrating émigrés into the political system of the Hungarian state. Citizenship policies include both extending political rights by

¹⁹⁰ “Refugee property in Hungary” 10 April 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁹¹ “Circular from Vienna Hungarian legation to Hungarian emigrants concerning citizenship” 5 December 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹² “Disappointment with émigré Hungarians” 11 September 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/10.

¹⁹³ “Wording of Refusal to persons applying for visit to relatives in the West” 13 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁴ “Népszabadság says defectors may return” 9 June 1975. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/1.

naturalisation, re-naturalisation or allowing dual citizenship,¹⁹⁵ and restricting political rights by loss of citizenship or renunciation of citizenship.¹⁹⁶

Another form of political incorporation is granting amnesty in an attempt to encourage émigrés to return to Hungary.¹⁹⁷ Sanctioning policies, for example, criminalising emigration,¹⁹⁸ might be seen as contradictory to incorporation; however, it is important to highlight that inverse incorporation also assumes that the state extends its control over the citizen. As in the case of all political incorporation policies, the interest of the state, instead of the interest of émigrés, provides the perspective for analysis. Therefore, even though incorporation might implicate beneficial policies, because of the interest of a closed regime, sanctioning policies are also included in this category.

The category of propaganda policies has three subcategories, two of them depicting the means of channelling propaganda, namely broadcasting “Homeland” radio programmes and press. The Homeland radio programme tried to engage with diasporans on several levels, it broadcast accounts of redefectors, letters of refugees and messages to emigrant relatives¹⁹⁹ in order to present an ideally depicted connection between émigrés and their relatives living in the home country. The radio programme also focused on the cultural developments and economic progress of the home state,²⁰⁰ as well as providing youth and sports programmes for the wider audience.²⁰¹

¹⁹⁵ “Hungarian House in Paris Advertises Consular Passports” 14 July 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁶ “Former Hungarian citizen visitors detained in Hungary,” HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14. And: “Means of obtaining release from Hungarian Citizenship” 15 March 1963. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁷ “Kádár announces amnesty” 22 March 1963. HU OSA 300-40-1:17/4.

¹⁹⁸ “Refugee sentenced in absentia” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.; “Campaign against refugees” 23 December 1965. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁹⁹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰¹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

As part of propaganda campaigns, the press had an effect predominantly on a domestic level, the majority of the archival records deals with how the press tried to formulate public opinion within state borders. Firstly, the press tried depicting émigré life as empty and dire, so citizens would give up their plans for leaving the country.²⁰² Another practice was to publish accounts by redefectors on the hardships of exile life or the letters of homesick exiles.²⁰³ The redefection campaign was also propagated by the press through the publishing of news on the campaign itself and representing the reunited families.²⁰⁴

A subcategory of propaganda policies is communication with émigrés. During the coding process, two types of communication were revealed within this category, encouraged communication and exploitive communication. It is important to highlight at this point that there is a crucial distinction between forced communication, which is discussed under control policies, and encouraged communication. The reason why these two types of communication are presented separately is the fact that according to the reports, encouraged communication served propaganda purposes,²⁰⁵ while forced communication, as was discussed earlier, served the purpose of controlling communication with émigrés.²⁰⁶ Exploitive communication also served the state propaganda by using émigrés to disseminate favourable information about Hungary abroad.²⁰⁷

The most immensely detailed diaspora engagement policy in the reports of RFE was the redefection policies. Generally, the redefection campaign of the state aimed at persuading émigrés to permanently return to Hungary, and perhaps this is the exact reason why Radio Free

²⁰² “The Situation of the Press – RFE” 7 December 1965. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

²⁰³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁵ “The regime’s attitude towards Hungarians living abroad,” HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

²⁰⁶ “Hungarian authorities’ interest in refugees’ reaction to consular passport” 27 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

²⁰⁷ “Emigráció, 1961-1986” 1963. HU OSA 300-40-3:9/64.

Europe made such an effort to report on that issue. *Table 1* lists the various elements of the redefection policies.

Extending appeals towards émigrés intended to emotionally manipulate émigrés to persuade them about returning. Within this category, the coding process revealed the subcategory of communicating the dissatisfaction of exile life by stressing the shameful and insulting conditions of émigrés' life and the hostile environment that surrounded them.²⁰⁸ The second subcategory is communicating about the economic interest of exiles through means of channelling state propaganda on the industrial progress of Hungary or the opportunities for employment.²⁰⁹ Awakening the sense of national identification and awakening the sense of family are describing actions through which the state aimed at creating the image of a welcoming homeland and family.²¹⁰

Redefection policies also include the subcategories of contacting émigrés and establishing institutions. Both of them emerged from the coding of reports that discussed forms of communication or establishment of institutions which concerned the redefection campaign of the state. In order to channel the campaign abroad, state representatives tried to personally approach émigrés²¹¹ or wrote official letters to get in touch with diasporans.²¹² To create the institutional background for the redefection campaign, the state set up repatriation committees and local information offices that provided assistance for redefectors.²¹³

The last two types of diaspora policies were social policies and symbolic policies. Social policies provided either social events for émigrés or aid for the ones in need. The subcategory

²⁰⁸ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁹ "Special Document issued to repatriates in Paris" 3 October 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/23.

²¹⁰ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²¹¹ "Visit of Hungarian legation officials to Hungarians now living and working in Wolverhampton" 17 August 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/22.

²¹² "Global analysis of the repatriation action" 6 October 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/23.

²¹³ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

of organising social activities refers to the reports which discussed social evenings organised by the Hungarian legation in foreign countries in order to attract diasporans and establish contact with them.²¹⁴ There is one report from 1959 which revealed that the Hungarian legation provided a free-of-charge dispensary²¹⁵ for diasporans in Paris, and another interesting report from 1985, which claims that the Hungarian state established pensioner homes for elderly returnees.²¹⁶ Even though these single reports do not discuss the social benefits in detail, they were included in the coding process as particular elements of diaspora engagement policies.

Symbolic policies are rarely mentioned in the reports of RFE, only a few instances reflect on the fact that even a dictatorial regime realised the importance of symbolic actions towards émigrés. Organising diaspora conferences first appears in the archival sources in 1983.²¹⁷ Diaspora conferences are aimed at providing a platform for engaging with members of the diasporic community and discussing issues regarding émigré life. Records on organising meetings with high-ranked state representatives date back to 1988, one of the most debated events was the meeting between Károly Grósz and émigrés in New York.²¹⁸

As we can see, the coding process resulted in the emergence of categories and subcategories of various types of diaspora engagement policies. Although the discussed codes introduce exciting topics to further analyse, it should be emphasised that only the perspective of Radio Free Europe is reflected in the reports on the diaspora engagement policies. Therefore, only meso-level analysis can be based on the typology presented above.

²¹⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²¹⁵ “The repatriation of Hungarian refugees from France survey of January 1959” 6 March 1959. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/18.

²¹⁶ “Emigráció, 1961-1986” 1985. HU OSA 300-40-3:9/64.

²¹⁷ “Association of Hungarians Meets in Budapest” 5 December 1983. HU OSA 300-40-1:1112/1.

²¹⁸ “Grosz and the Hungarian emigre community in the USA” 3 August 1988. HU OSA 300-40-2:22/3.

Contextualising Diaspora Policies

After a closer look at the established typology of the Hungarian diaspora policies, there are a number of parallels that can be drawn between the diaspora policies of the satellite states. Radio Free Europe, as a covert organisation of the CIA, aimed at channelling propaganda to the Soviet bloc countries.²¹⁹ The different units of Radio Free Europe created background reports on the so-called Soviet satellite states and their diasporas in order to provide a broad perspective for the anti-Communist propaganda. As Michael Cude and Ellen Paul point out regarding Czech and Slovak émigrés' role at RFE, their contribution meant that the anti-Communist perspective of the exile community could reach Czechoslovakia through the broadcasts.²²⁰ Reports on the Czechoslovak, Polish, and Romanian diaspora policies predominantly dealt with the redefection campaign of the satellite states. As a report from January 1956 details,²²¹ one of the most influential efforts of the Soviet bloc regimes was the redefection campaign which aimed at refugees living in camps in Germany and Austria, but also at the broader rank and file of the exile community in Western countries. The methods that were applied by the Soviet bloc countries show some similarities with the Hungarian redefection campaign.

The redefection campaign of the Czechoslovak state applied various methods to persuade refugees and émigrés to return to their home country. One of these methods was a letter campaign in which redefectors were forced to write letters to exiles about the appeals of returning to the home country, describing all the benefits that were offered by the state to the returnees.²²² Extorted letters were a method often used by campaigns of other satellite states as well, given the personal tone of those letters and the potential emotional manipulation that the letters could mean in the hands of the state authorities. Similar methods were observed in the

²¹⁹ Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 3.

²²⁰ Michael Cude and Ellen Paul, "Czechoslovakia," in *East Central European Migrations During the Cold War*, ed. Anna Mazurkiewicz (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2019), 122.

²²¹ "Recent Aspects of the Redefection Campaign" 16 January 1956. HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 16-25.

²²² "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 17-18.

Polish Unit of Radio Free Europe. The methods used by the Polish state show a rich variety of practices: letter-writing, personal approaches, and organisational work to reach exiled communities or individuals.²²³ The same practice can be observed in the case of the Hungarian state as well, which tried to exploit returnees to channel redefection propaganda home and abroad.²²⁴

Redefectors were used for propaganda purposes not only in the letter-writing campaign. As one of the reports of the Hungarian Unit of RFE puts it: “As a rule, all returnees are exploited for the same propaganda purposes: they depict life in the West with the gloomiest colours and have bitter words against the Western broadcasting stations, among them also against RFE for having moved them to escape the country by lies.”²²⁵ Another report alleges that forced interviews were made with returnees during which scripted answers were given to the authorities.²²⁶

Soviet satellite states commonly established an institutional background for their respective redefection campaigns. In the case of Czechoslovakia, the institutional background for the campaign was provided by the “Committee to Care for Amnestied Refugees Returning to Czechoslovakia”, interestingly – as the report highlights – no notable or prominent Communist political figure contributed openly to the committee or the campaign.²²⁷ The official state representation in the redefection campaign were the embassies that contacted local exiles to inform them about the amnesty decrees and the possibility to return to the home state.²²⁸ This distinct separation of state institutions from repatriation committees and the concealing of state involvement in the work of committees are recurring elements of the reports. In the case of Romania, the institutional background for the redefection campaign was also carefully designed

²²³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 28.

²²⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 7-9.

²²⁵ “Re-emigrants” 21 September 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/19.

²²⁶ “Interrogation of redefectors” 10 April 1957. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/18.”

²²⁷ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 19.

²²⁸ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 21.

by setting up the “Committee for Repatriation” which had authority over the publication of newspapers and the operation of a radio station in order to facilitate the return of émigrés.²²⁹

Contrary to the Czechoslovak case, the repatriation committee in Romania included well-known Communist political figures.²³⁰

Meanwhile, sources on the Hungarian redefection campaign use different names for the institutional background. One report from 1956 refers to a “repatriation committee”²³¹ that served the interest of the Hungarian campaign, and another source from 1958 makes a reference to a “Committee to Promote the Return Home of Hungarians.”²³² A report of the Hungarian Unit from 1957 refers to “the repatriation commissions which are working under the supervision of the Legation”²³³ and later adds: “In other countries, the whole redefection procedure is handled by the Legations.”²³⁴ Not only the Hungarian Legation involved itself in the redefection campaign; but reports on the Czechoslovak campaign also claimed that local embassies were in contact with exile diasporans to channel the news about the opportunity of returning to their home state.²³⁵

Channelling the propaganda about the redefection campaign was done through various means. In the Czechoslovakian campaign, the publication of *Hlas Domova* (Voice of Homeland) magazine served this purpose, because it was circulated among exile communities.²³⁶ The magazine provided information about redefectors experiences after returning to Czechoslovakia, and also about amnesty decrees issued by the home state. The Czechoslovakian state – in some way or another – tried to channel the following appeals

²²⁹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39.

²³⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39-40.

²³¹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 8.

²³² “The East Berlin Repatriation Committee” 12 February 1958. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/17.

²³³ “Redefection propaganda and procedure” 6 April 1957. HU OSA 300-40-1:258/2.

²³⁴ “Redefection propaganda and procedure,” HU OSA 300-40-1:258/2.

²³⁵ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 21.

²³⁶ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 17-19.

towards émigrés: economic prosperity in the home state, personal free life at home, dissatisfactions of exile life, a sense of family, and a sense of national identification.²³⁷ The reports show a simple formula: the state depicted an ideal and free life with economic benefits for returnees, while also degrading the exiled way of life and evoking a sense of guilt in émigrés for leaving their home country and relatives behind.

The Polish state introduced a radio broadcast entitled *Kraj* (Homeland) to reach out to the diaspora.²³⁸ The well-orchestrated communication channels served the propaganda machinery of the Polish state in order to provide information on the home country that could counterbalance the anti-Communist propaganda from politically active exile communities. The target of the propaganda campaign was, at first, the professionals and intellectuals of the émigré community. Later, the focus of the campaign broadened and included refugees in general.²³⁹ Thus, we can see that considerable attention was directed to creating and gradually building up the state propaganda in order to successfully reach émigrés and convince them to return to their home states.

Contrary to the appeals of the Czechoslovak redefection propaganda, the Polish campaign had two basic appeals: a sense of national identification and dissatisfaction with exile life; however, it put more emphasis on discrediting the leaders of politically active members of the emigration.²⁴⁰ The importance of the sense of national identification was a recurring theme of Polish state propaganda, which tried to establish a monopoly over Polish culture, language, and history.²⁴¹ Interestingly, while the redefection campaign in both the Czechoslovak and the Polish cases made considerable efforts to communicate the appeals of returning home, neither

²³⁷ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 24-25.

²³⁸ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 28.

²³⁹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 26-27.

²⁴⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 37-38.

²⁴¹ “East European Governments’ Attitude,” HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2, 33.

visa nor passport policies were propagated openly to provide possible returnees with information on the means of re-entering the home state.

The Romanian Committee for Repatriation published a newspaper entitled *Glasul Patriei* (Voice of Homeland), and it propagated similar appeals to the previously mentioned Czechoslovak and Polish campaigns, namely the hardships of exile life, the economic progress in the homeland and employment opportunities.²⁴² Comparing these reports to the Hungarian campaign presents a vast variety of the already-mentioned appeals. The first appeal is awakening “the sense of family” by picturing “the loneliness of the loved ones at home”, “the need for help at home”, “the forgiveness for having deserted the home” and the “loving arms of the family”.²⁴³ The second major appeal is the “economic self-interest” of exiles evoked by channelling “opportunities for employment at home” and presenting the “industrial expansion and progress at home”.²⁴⁴ The third appeal is “national identification” provoked by creating the picture of the “welcoming home”, the “forgiveness for having sinned against the Fatherland”, the “nobility of the Fatherland”, the “history and folklore of Hungary” and the “symbols of the Fatherland.”²⁴⁵ The last appeal is presenting the “dissatisfactions of exile life” by depicting the “lonesomeness, solitude, rootlessness of exile” life, the “hostile environment surrounding the exile”, the “shameful and insulting conditions of exile life” and émigrés’ “treatment as a foreigner.”²⁴⁶

The Hungarian campaign utilised both the radio and the press as well. The Homeland radio programme targeted Hungarian émigrés living in Western European countries, but residents of Hungary were also considered as the target audience. As the report suggests, the fact “that the

²⁴² “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 40.

²⁴³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁵ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁶ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

programs were also designed to implement the domestic aspects of the redefection campaign is suggested by the fact that they are transmitted on both the short and medium (Kossuth) wavebands.”²⁴⁷ The Hungarian state also published a periodical entitled *Magyar Hírek* (Hungarian News), and some reports reflect on the distribution of the paper: “The World Federation of Hungarians publishes a periodical called *Magyar Hírek* (Hungarian News) which appears twice a month and of which 85,000 free copies are sent abroad. It also produces a calendar every December.”²⁴⁸

Apart from the many similarities, the reports of the national Units of RFE contain some peculiarities, such as a report on the attempts of the Romanian state to penetrate the émigré community by sending abroad priests of the Bucharest Orthodox Patriarchy.²⁴⁹ The cooperation of the state and church concerning diaspora engagement policies was seemingly not observed or analysed in the Czechoslovak or Polish cases. A reappearing endeavour in the reports is the issuance of amnesty decrees. The reports of the Romanian Unit highlight the impact of the amnesty decree of 1955, which pardoned all crimes (except for murder) committed by Romanian citizens living in exile at that time, in case they decided to return to Romania.²⁵⁰

The means and methods of engaging with the diasporas of the satellite states were apparently rather similar. However, it has to be emphasised that since the origin of these reports in all cases is Radio Free Europe, this common origin surely had its impact on the creation, and hence, the similarities of the reports. By contextualising the primary sources of the research and carrying out a systematic analysis of the developed typology and the existing literature on the topic, my

²⁴⁷ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 6-7.

²⁴⁸ “World Federation of Hungarians Situation Report” 27 April 1976. HU OSA 300-40-1:1112/5.

²⁴⁹ “East European Governments’ Attitude,” HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2, 38.

²⁵⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39.

paper attempted to draw results that could be relevant to the framework of diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War era.

Conclusion

Modern diaspora studies put considerable emphasis on creating explanatory frameworks and typologies for a better understanding of diaspora policies. However, the typologies discussed earlier have not treated the context of the examined policies in much detail. This led us to the realisation that in spite of the numerous studies about diaspora policy-making, there is a research gap to be further explored. The significance of the present study lies in the fact that it is based on the qualitative method of thematic analysis. Although qualitative research is suitable only for the analysis of smaller amounts of data, it can explore deeper correlations owing to its capability to construct concepts and typologies, instead of only providing descriptive analysis.

This study, therefore, explored diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War era by analysing reports of the different units of Radio Free Europe as primary sources of the research. The aim of the research was to investigate how diaspora engagement policies are reflected in the sources and to reveal the interconnections between diaspora policies of Soviet bloc countries. The key results of this analysis were summarized in the typology of diaspora policies.

The typology of diaspora engagement policies that I developed as a result of the archival research differentiates ten major categories of diaspora policies: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies. The categories, subcategories, and codes of diaspora policies provided an insight into how Radio Free Europe perceived state-diaspora relations. Moreover, they helped to detect what further primary sources should be analysed, due to the fact that the emerging categories shed light on the mechanisms of diaspora policy-making. Therefore, future research should be

carried out that includes more diverse types of primary sources, which could help to reach theoretical saturation.

The study revealed that exploring the Cold War diaspora policy-making in the context of the Soviet bloc states provides deep analytical opportunities. As the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian cases proved, there are numerous parallels to be drawn between the diaspora policies of the satellite states. The sources shed light on the common historical context that could also serve as a basis for future research, since the comparative analysis of the diaspora policies of the Soviet satellite states is hitherto an untapped research field. The paper also showed that, although several researches explored the state-diaspora nexus so far, no comprehensive research has been carried out yet which could integrate the various aspects of state-diaspora relations.

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Europe as a Pentarchy? - Peacekeeping, Balance of Power, and the Congress System as Early Forms of European Integration

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Abstract

This paper discusses the cooperative potential of the great power system in post-Napoleonic Europe – the Pentarchy – and argues that the predominant policies of peacekeeping and “balance of power” as well as the short period of regular diplomatic congresses after 1815 point towards an early form of European integration. It thereby challenges the prevalent narrative of the process of European unification as a unique development that only began after World War II. The possibilities for and tendencies towards inter-state cooperation and supranational governance within the framework of the Pentarchy are shown by examining three of its successive core characteristics: firstly, a general understanding to avoid bellicose conflicts to keep the peace and ensure political stability during the monarchist restoration; secondly, a highly dynamic balance of power policy to facilitate peacekeeping and to counter hegemonic ambitions of any great power; and thirdly, the institutionalised format of the Congress system to jointly resolve European affairs and balance great power interests during regular meetings. Based on diplomatic documents and treaties as well as the observations of statesmen, politicians and political commentators, the analysis shows how the Pentarchy created spaces for increased cooperation between European states and conservative governments with concurrent interests. Consequently, the paper dismisses the topos of the nineteenth century as the era of the isolated nation-state and argues that the Pentarchy system functioned as a precursor of modern European integration.

Introduction

European integration is often understood as a process of post-1945 unification, which is primarily a consequence of the devastating wars of the first half of the twentieth century. It is seen as a project meant to ensure peace and prosperity in the form of a continually intensifying cooperation between European states.²⁵¹ This narrative is mainly based on economic and politico-economic institutions and depicts the development from the European Coal and Steel Community towards the European Union as an almost teleological pattern in history. There is no room in this story for the developments before 1945, without which European integration can hardly be explained. The demarcation of European integration in the post-war period from European history of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, which is still clearly recognisable in historiography, thus still makes the current political unification process appear as a unique phenomenon anchored exclusively in contemporary history.²⁵²

In this paper, I transfer the idea of a political union of Europe into the nineteenth century and discuss the so-called *Pentarchy*²⁵³ of the great powers as a precursor of modern European integration. Of course, the state system created after 1815 cannot be equated with the numerous supranational institutions of the EU. But the politics of balance of power and transnational congresses of the post-Napoleonic *Concert of Europe*²⁵⁴ are connected to a relatively peaceful

²⁵¹ See e.g. Bruno Zandonella, "Europäische Integration," in *Pocket Europa. EU-Begriffe und Länderdaten*, ed. Bruno Zandonella (Bonn: Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, 2005), accessed September 15, 2022, <https://www.bpb.de/nachschlagen/lexika/pocket-europa/16687/europaeische-integration>; or Otto Schmuck, "Motive und Leitbilder der europäischen Einigung," *Informationen zur politischen Bildung* 279 (2015): 7-16.

²⁵² Wolfram Kaiser criticises the lack of "connections across World War II," see Wolfram Kaiser, "From Isolation to Centrality. Contemporary History Meets European Studies," in *European Union History. Themes and Debates*, ed. Wolfram Kaiser and Antonio Varsori (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), 45-65, here 50.

²⁵³ The terms "Pentarchy" and "Concert of Europe" are often used interchangeably (see footnote 4), but the former is less common and could describe any rule of five. It is used as a description of the European state system e.g. in Irby C. Nichols, *The European Pentarchy and the Congress of Verona, 1822* (Den Haag: Martinus Nijhoff, 1971); or in Hugo Hantsch, "Metternich und Europa," *Der Donauraum. Zeitschrift des Instituts für den Donauraum und Mitteleuropa* 10, no. 4 (1965): 193-203, here 197; or in Paul W. Schroeder, "Did the Vienna Settlement Rest on a Balance of Power?" *The American Historical Review* 97, no. 3 (1992): 683-706, here 688.

²⁵⁴ "Concert of Europe" is the prevalent term describing the European Pentarchy in the nineteenth century and is often used in the historiography of international relations, see e.g. Richard B. Elrod, "The Concert of Europe. A

era, and they bore institutionalised features – which this paper will argue can be seen as an early form of European integration.

Analysing early forms of integration is not a new field of historical research, especially regarding the nineteenth century. I refer to the works of Hartmut Kaelble, Claude Conter, Ulrich Lappenküper, Guido Thiemeyer and Isabel Tölle.²⁵⁵ In many cases, research focuses on a cultural or social history of Europe, the emergence of a European self-perception, or the economic coalescence of the continent. The political perspective, however, is somewhat neglected – the nineteenth century is perceived as the era of national movements and nation-states inhibiting any form of integration. René Girault observes the principle that the stronger the nation-states get, the more Europe falls apart.²⁵⁶

This statement can hardly be rejected in the face of the national wars of unification in the nineteenth century and the world wars of the twentieth century. At the same time, however, it cannot be denied that the European state system of the nineteenth century functioned as a Concert with certain patterns of interstate cooperation, and even a policy of international congresses to settle European issues.²⁵⁷ So even if national interests were paramount: diplomacy and policies on the European level remain an indispensable field of research to understand the

Fresh Look at an International System,” *World Politics* 28, no. 2 (1976): 159-174; Charles A. Kupchan and Clifford A. Kupchan, “Concerts, Collective Security, and the Future of Europe,” *International Security* 16, no. 1 (1991): 114-161; Branislav L. Slantchev, “Territory and Commitment. The Concert of Europe as Self-Enforcing Equilibrium,” *Security Studies* 14, no. 4 (2005); see also Claude D. Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten und Modeeuropäer. Antriebskräfte des Europadiskurses zwischen 1815 und 1848,” in *Europäische Einigung im 19. und 20. Jahrhundert. Akteure und Antriebskräfte*, ed. Ulrich Lappenküper and Guido Thiemeyer (Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh, 2013), 23-43, here 30-32.

²⁵⁵ See e.g. Hartmut Kaelble, *Europäer über Europa. Die Entstehung des europäischen Selbstverständnisses im 19. und 20. Jahrhundert* (Frankfurt a.M.: Campus Verlag, 2001); Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten”; Guido Thiemeyer and Isabel Tölle, “Supranationalität im 19. Jahrhundert? Die Beispiele der Zentralkommission für die Rheinschiffahrt und des Octroivertrages 1804-1851,” *Journal of European Integration History* 17, no. 2 (2011): 177-196.

²⁵⁶ “[...] eine für lange Zeit gültige Gesetzmäßigkeit [...]: je mehr sich der Nationalstaat konsolidiert, desto mehr fällt Europa auseinander und desto weniger können europäische Institutionen gegründet werden,” René Girault, “Das Europa der Historiker,” in *Europa im Blick der Historiker*, ed. Rainer Hudemann, Hartmut Kaelble and Klaus Schwabe (Munich: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 1995), 55-90, here 63. Translation done by the author.

²⁵⁷ Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 30-32.

history and origins of modern European integration processes. It is in this sense that Eric Hobsbawm writes about the emergence of Europe as a community of states as well as an idea: “First, it emerged as an international state system”.²⁵⁸

I want to discuss three characteristics of the integrative potential of the state system created after 1815. Firstly, I will focus on peacekeeping as a main objective of the Concert of Europe and as a cooperation basis for European governments; secondly, I want to highlight the balance of power politics within the Pentarchy as the guiding principle to facilitate the collaboration of the great powers; and thirdly, I will discuss the already mentioned policy of international congresses as an institutionalised supranational format of negotiation. These three aspects cannot be discussed in all their complexity – the goal is to show their neglected European dimension. Although the Pentarchy and the Concert of Europe persisted in the second half of the nineteenth century and the early twentieth century respectively, I will only focus on the first half of the nineteenth century.²⁵⁹ As primary sources, I use mostly diplomatic documents presenting the cooperation within the Pentarchy, or political observations by German-speaking critics of the post-Napoleonic state-system.

Peacekeeping and restoration as a pan-European task

After the Napoleonic wars, a system of states was established in Europe that was largely controlled by five great powers. This Pentarchy consisted of the “Big Four and France”²⁶⁰, i.e. the most important members of the anti-Napoleonic alliance – Russia, Prussia, Austria and Great Britain – as well as France, whose status as a great power was preserved (or restored) in the course of the Congress of Vienna.²⁶¹ At this Congress, the European states not only redrew

²⁵⁸ Eric Hobsbawm, *On History* (New York: The New Press, 1997), 225.

²⁵⁹ More explicitly, this means the years between 1815 and 1853. The Crimean War (1853-56) was the first major war between European great powers since the Napoleonic Wars, and is considered a turning point, if not the end of the European Concert, see Kupchan and Kupchan, “Concerts,” 122; or Slantchev, “Territory,” 601-604.

²⁶⁰ Slantchev, “Territory,” 585.

²⁶¹ See Ulrich Lappenküper, “Frühformen politischer Einigung Europas. Metternich und das Europäische Konzert,” in *Europäische Einigung im 19. und 20. Jahrhundert. Akteure und Antriebskräfte*, ed. Ulrich

the political borders of the continent – they also began the process of establishing a European system of peacekeeping and equilibrium, carried by the five great powers, to counter revolutionary upheavals as well as hegemonic aspirations of any single power.²⁶²

This already hints at the balance of power policy explained below. In any case, securing the status quo of the Congress of Vienna was an objective to be achieved by avoiding bellicose conflicts and suppressing revolutionary tendencies. The twenty-five years of conflict during and after the French Revolution had highlighted the transnational nature of war and revolution throughout Europe, which is why equally international cooperation of conservative and monarchist forces seemed necessary to avoid them.²⁶³ Prince Metternich, often regarded as the architect of the “Vienna Settlement”²⁶⁴, therefore considered the cooperation of European governments to be indispensable for the preservation of peace, especially in terms of the suppression of revolutionary movements:

It is time for all the governments of Europe, whatever their constitutional form, to realise that solitary action is no longer equal to the gravity of the malady; that the common cause of them all is at stake; that they must act, in the same spirit and by joint measures [...] and that the necessity of their self-preservation imposes upon them the duty of helping each other of their own free will [...].²⁶⁵

Lappenküper and Guido Thiemeyer (Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh, 2013), 117-135, here 119; for a detailed description see Henry Kissinger, “The Congress of Vienna. A Reappraisal,” *World Politics* 8, no. 2 (1956): 264-280, here 268, 276.

²⁶² Günter Wollstein, “Europa unter Modernisierungsdruck,” *Informationen zur politischen Bildung* 265 (2010): par. 13, accessed September 16, 2022, <http://www.bpb.de/izpb/9870/europa-unter-modernisierungsdruck?p=all>.

²⁶³ See e.g. Lappenküper, “Frühformen,” 124-29. A good example is the “Circulaire finale” of the Congress of Verona, “Kongress von Verona IX. Circulaire finale,” in *Mächtekongresse 1818–1822*, ed. Karin Schneider (Vienna: Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, 2018), accessed September 17, 2022, https://maechtekongresse.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/pages/show.html?document=Verona_IX_1.xml&directory=editions.

²⁶⁴ Schroeder, “Vienna Settlement,” 638; see also Slantchev, “Territory,” 569.

²⁶⁵ “*Es ist Zeit, daß alle Regierungen Europas, welches auch immer ihre Verfassungsform sein mag, zu der Einsicht gelangen, daß isolierte Maßnahmen der Schwere des Übels nicht mehr gewachsen sind; daß es um ihrer aller gemeinsame Sache geht; daß sie handeln müssen, im gleichen Geist und durch gemeinsame Maßnahmen [...] und daß die Notwendigkeit ihrer Selbsterhaltung ihnen die Pflicht auferlegt, einander aus freien Stücken zu helfen [...]*,” “Instruktion Metternichs an den österreichischen Gesandten in der Schweiz Baron von Binder,” June 9, 1826, in *Quellen zur Ära Metternich*, ed. Elisabeth Droß (Darmstadt: wbg Academic, 1999), 124-125, here 125. Translation done by the author.

The differences between the Pentarchy states are thus emphasised far less than their similarities, and the latter are justified by the commitment against a common enemy in the form of revolutionary movements.²⁶⁶ The suppression of democratic and liberal forces in the course of the conservative-monarchical restoration was particularly severe in Prussia, Russia and Austria: After the victory over France, the three monarchies concluded the so-called Holy Alliance “to protect religion, peace and justice”.²⁶⁷ Although the actual influence of this alliance has often been overestimated, the fact that all European states except Great Britain and the Papal States joined the alliance shows that there was a general agreement and willingness to cooperate between them, even to the point of creating political treaties and rules²⁶⁸ – although it should be noted that the treaty of the monarchs merely formulated a rather vague “rule of conduct”.²⁶⁹ This policy of internal repression and external peace advocated by these governments was opposed by liberals and nationalists who doubted the stability of the Viennese order and saw in nation-states a greater chance for a peaceful and secure political framework for Europe.²⁷⁰ This was particularly the case in central Europe, since the German Confederation created in 1815 did not satisfy the expectations regarding a unified German state. According to Wollstein, the loose, federal architecture of the Confederation made it a “buffer in the centre of Europe”²⁷¹

²⁶⁶ The “Circulaire” of Verona laments the way in which the “honest and sincere intentions of the monarchs” are perceived and misinterpreted: “[...] *les fausses alarmes, les interprétations hostiles, les prédictions sinistres que l’ignorance et la mauvaise foi avaient fait retentir en Europe pour égarer l’opinion des peuples sur les intentions franches et loyales des Monarques!*”, and continues to describe the objective of the monarchs: “*résister à la révolution; prévenir les désordres, les crimes, les calamités innombrables [...]; y rétablir l’ordre et la paix [...]* – tel a été l’unique objet des pensées et des efforts des Monarques,” see “Kongress von Verona IX. Circulaire finale”. Translation done by the author.

²⁶⁷ “[...] *pour protéger la religion, la paix et la justice,*” “Sainte Alliance entre L. L. M. M. l’Empereur de toutes les Russies, l’Empereur d’Autriche et le Roi de Prusse, signé à Paris le 26 Septembre 1815,” in *Corpus iuris Confoederationis Germanicae oder Staatsacten für Geschichte und öffentliches Recht des Deutschen Bundes*, 1: Staatsverträge, ed. Philipp A. G. Meyer (Frankfurt a.M.: H. L. Brönnner, 3rd ed., 1858), 290-291, here 290. Translation done by the author.

²⁶⁸ Lappenküper, “Frühformen,” 122-123; Stella Ghervas, “Ein Palimpsest für den Frieden. Die Heilige Allianz und das Ende des französischen Empire,” in *Die Heilige Allianz. Entstehung - Wirkung - Rezeption*, ed. Anselm Schubert and Wolfram Pyta (Stuttgart: Kohlhammer Verlag, 2018), 61-78, here 61, 64,77.

²⁶⁹ “[...] *règle de leur conduit,*” “Sainte Alliance,” 290. Translation done by the author.

²⁷⁰ Kaelble, *Europäer über Europa*, 55-56.

²⁷¹ “[...] *Puffer in der Mitte Europas,*” Wollstein, “Europa,” par. 15. Translation done by the author.

which had been used as a repressive instrument by Metternich since 1819 at the latest. The German Confederation certainly corresponded to the restorative approach of the Pentarchy and its restrained foreign policy, but in the eyes of the national movement it remained a danger for the entire continent: the liberal German writer and politician Johann Georg August Wirth wrote that without a unified Germany there could be no stable organisation and salvation for Europe: “without it [i.e. the political unity of Germany] there is [...] no prospect of a durable organisation of this part of the world and no salvation for Europe!”²⁷²

It is certainly possible to interpret the fear of national unrest and revolution as a driving force behind the political actions of the European cabinets, which subsequently depended on a general peacekeeping policy. According to Richard Elwood, the great powers thus had “the responsibility of preserving the peace of Europe and of protecting a European society menaced by revolutionary principles”²⁷³. Whether a European society existed as such, or whether the cabinets and statesmen perceived themselves and their political agenda primarily as “European” is highly debatable – but the necessity of peace and the implementation of a pan-European peacekeeping policy certainly had an integrative effect. According to Conter, the European elites made genuinely European decisions²⁷⁴ that contributed to securing peace on the continent. Probably the most important cornerstone of this peace order was the balance of power between the great powers. In the following section, the balance of power within the Pentarchy will therefore be explained in more detail.

²⁷² “[...] ohne sie [i.e. die politische Einheit Deutschlands] giebt es [...] keine Aussicht zu dauerhafter Organisation des Welttheils und kein Heil für Europa!” Johann G. A. Wirth, *Die politische Reform Deutschlands. Noch ein dringendes Wort an die deutschen Volksfreunde* (Strasbourg: privately printed, 1832), 15; see also Kaelble, *Europäer über Europa*, 55-56. Translation done by the author.

²⁷³ Elrod, “The Concert of Europe,” 164.

²⁷⁴ “[...] genuin europäische Entscheidungen,” Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 30. Translation done by the author.

Balance of Power as a security strategy

However necessary inter-state cooperation was to preserve peace and the status quo – there remained a strong reluctance towards a supranational European unity, as Hartmut Kaelble explains.²⁷⁵ This was due to the widespread fear, amplified by the Napoleonic campaigns, of a hegemonic country under the guise of European unification. Such apprehensions gave rise to the Pentarchy after 1815, a multipolar system in which the ambitions of individual great powers were kept in check by the others. The character of this system has been much debated – and it remains unclear whether the emerging Concert of the five great powers was a self-perpetuating system of equilibrium without political vision, a conservative restoration project supported by active balance politics, or whether there were actually five great powers involved at all.²⁷⁶

What is undisputed, however, is the general observation that there was a balance of power based on several states. This should not obscure the fact that terms such as *equilibrium* or *balance of power* are highly problematic: Randall Schweller calls the latter “a notoriously slippery, murky, and protean term, endlessly debated and variously defined”²⁷⁷ and refers to seven different meanings, while Paul W. Schroeder even lists eleven possible interpretations.²⁷⁸ In view of the small scope of this paper, I will consider *balance of power* according to a brief and simple definition by Godfried van Benthem van den Bergh, who refers to its processual character and explains it as follows: “a policy to prevent a bid for hegemony of one of the Great Powers, by

²⁷⁵ “[...] Zurückhaltung [...] gegenüber einer supranationalen Einheit Europas,” Kaelble, *Europäer über Europa*, 58. Translation done by the author.

²⁷⁶ See Maartje Abbenhuis, *An Age of Neutrals. Great Power Politics, 1815-1914* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 39-46; Paul W. Schroeder, “The 19th-Century International System. Changes in the Structure,” *World Politics* 39, no. 1 (1986): 1-26, here 9-10; Slantchev, “Territory,” 565-567, 573-575.

²⁷⁷ Randall L. Schweller, “The Balance of Power in World Politics,” *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics* (2016): 1-20, here 1.

²⁷⁸ Schweller, “The Balance of Power,” 3-4; Paul W. Schroeder, “The nineteenth century system. Balance of power or political equilibrium?” *Review of International Studies* 15 (1989): 135-153, here 137.

the threat of the other Great Powers allying against it.”²⁷⁹ Thus, the cooperation of the great powers was encouraged and enforced, even though their rivalry never ended.

This pattern of interpretation corresponds perfectly to the political situation after 1815.²⁸⁰ Even at the Congress of Vienna, various camps and coalitions were formed that balanced each other out, and often the political balancing manoeuvres were characterised by cooperation and power struggle in equal measure.²⁸¹ It is hardly surprising that the national and democratic forces saw reason to criticise such diplomatic trade-offs and political moves: Wirth portrays the dynastic balance of power policy based on the equality of “physical masses” as ridiculous and nonsensical. In his view, a “natural” equilibrium could only be established through freedom and (national) identity of all peoples.²⁸²

However, there is no such balance of “physical masses” per se, at least when one considers the distribution of power between the individual great powers. Some historians have therefore further subdivided the European system of states; Maartje Abbenhuis, for example, assumes two hegemonic powers (Great Britain and Russia) and three middle powers (Austria, France, Prussia).²⁸³ Prussia was the weakest great power, a fact that was not lost on contemporaries. The inferiority of the Prussian state in terms of area, demographics and military strength, especially in relation to its eastern neighbour, even led critics of the Hohenzollern monarchy to

²⁷⁹ Godfried van Benthem van den Bergh, “Balance of Power, History of,” in *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, ed. James D. Wright (Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2nd ed., 2015), 345-348, here 345.

²⁸⁰ It should be noted that the principles of a European Pentarchy and equilibrium already shaped the political situation in eighteenth century Europe, see e.g. Wolfgang Schmale, “Europa als Topos der Geschichtsschreibung,” in *Auf der Suche nach einem Phantom? Widerspiegelungen Europas in der Geschichtswissenschaft*, ed. Georg Michels (Baden-Baden: Nomos Verlag, 2003), 45-67, here 54-55; for a detailed overview of the developments in the eighteenth century I recommend Heinz Duchhardt, *Balance of Power und Pentarchie. Internationale Beziehungen 1700–1785* (Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh, 1997).

²⁸¹ An example is the Polish-Saxonian crisis of 1814, see Lappenküper, “Frühformen,” 119; Matthew Rendall, “Defensive realism and the Concert of Europe,” *Review of International Studies* 32 (2006): 523–540, here 526-530.

²⁸² “Das europäische Gleichgewicht, das die Dynastien bisher auf eine ebenso lächerliche als unsinnige Weise durch gleiches Abwägen physischer Massen herzustellen bemüht waren, hat alsdann in dem Prinzip der Freiheit und der Identität [...] aller Völker seinen natürlichen Stützpunkt gefunden,” Wirth, *Die politische Reform*, 326. Translation done by the author.

²⁸³ Abbenhuis, *An Age of Neutrals*, 41.

accuse it of being dominated by Russia. The Austrian politician Franz Schuselka wrote of Frederick II's successors that they had been reduced to Russian “wards”.²⁸⁴ This statement, although exaggerated, is rather consistent with Abbenhuis' considerations.

Nevertheless, the balance of power policy succeeded in post-Napoleonic Europe because it created a dynamic security system based on cooperation and equilibrium rather than confrontation.²⁸⁵ Matthew Rendall attributes the fact that any superiority of individual states was not transformed into a hegemonic position to the prevailing principle of “defensive realism”²⁸⁶, i.e. a restraint created solely by the fear of a hostile superiority. At the same time, some theorists argue that any balance, once created, is self-sustaining as an autopoietic system, since no community of roughly equal-ranking states allows the emergence of a hegemonic power.²⁸⁷ The definition of the balance of power described above thus becomes a “natural” phenomenon functioning without any normative or ideological background. This focus on the self-interests of states as well as the logical self-preservation of the system naturally casts doubt on whether the order created after 1815 was anything more than a power struggle based on *realpolitik* and constant *zugzwang*.

On the other hand, the European balance of power in the early nineteenth century can also be linked to a community of values: According to Kupchan and Kupchan, the European community of states after 1815 was a prime example of “collective security”²⁸⁸: Such a security arises when, firstly, no state becomes more powerful than a coalition of other states against it –

²⁸⁴ “[...] zuletzt gänzlich in die Stellung eines russischen Schützlings und Mündels herabgekommen,” Franz Schuselka, *Deutschland, Polen und Rußland* (Hamburg: Hoffmann und Campe, 1846), 193. Translation done by the author.

²⁸⁵ An interesting contribution to the discussion about the failure of the balance of power politics was written by Stacie Goddard, although it regards the wars of German unification, which I cannot discuss in this paper. See Stacie E. Goddard, “When Might Makes Right. How Prussia Overturned the European Balance of Power,” *International Security* 33, no. 3 (2009): 110-142.

²⁸⁶ Rendall, “Defensive Realism,” 523 and the short explanation on 524.

²⁸⁷ Slantchev calls it a “self-enforcing equilibrium,” Slantchev, “Territory,” 567.

²⁸⁸ Kupchan and Kupchan, “Concerts,” 122-124.

this corresponds to the above-mentioned definition by van Benthem van den Bergh. But beyond that, collective security assumes, secondly, a rough convergence of political convictions in the participating states, and thirdly, it emphasises a certain degree of solidarity between governments.²⁸⁹ The Pentarchy after the Congress of Vienna, which was concerned with peacekeeping and restoration, certainly fulfils these conditions: Not only did alliances such as the Holy Alliance and the Quadruple Alliance counter hegemonic aspirations of any great power in Europe, but the involved governments also shared many conservative, anti-revolutionary or monarchist views, and, as shown above, the threat of political upheaval ensured a degree of reactionary inter-governmental solidarity. The balance of powers policy thus created a security system of shared values.²⁹⁰

With regard to the theory-laden question of the natural self-preservation of a balanced power system as a consequence of a mutual blockade of competing states, I agree with Schweller's opinion: "From the policymaker's perspective, [...] balancing superior power and filling power vacuums hardly appear as laws of nature."²⁹¹ This statement is relevant at this point insofar as it does not simply question the predictability of a balancing system, but rather emphasises the actors: European monarchs and statesmen had to work actively to maintain balance and could not rely on regularities formulated in theory. One consequence of their efforts was the emergence of the congress principle, which was to further stabilise the international order and which I will briefly discuss in the next part of the paper.

²⁸⁹ Kupchan and Kupchan, "Concerts," 124-125.

²⁹⁰ Regarding the Concert of Europe, Lappenküper mentions solidarity between the great powers for peacekeeping and suppressing liberal forces ("*Großmachtsolidarität zur Bewahrung des Friedens [...] und Unterdrückung der liberalen Kräfte*"), Lappenküper, "Frühformen," 124.

²⁹¹ Schweller, "The Balance of Power," 2.

The Congress System as a European Institution

The balance policy was a fundamental principle of foreign policy that was pursued by the great powers primarily to maintain their own power, but at the same time was shaped by certain shared values and the recognition of the need for greater inter-state cooperation. But even if the balance of powers was a generally recognised and accepted guideline in foreign policy, it remained an informal principle not regulated by treaty: “Collective action emerged through informal negotiations, not through formal mechanisms [...]. Decisions were reached through consensus; there was no unanimity rule or veto.”²⁹² In the first years after the Congress of Vienna, however, the policy of balance and cooperation underwent a form of deliberate institutionalisation.

This took place not only through the establishment of the European Concert, but also through an official, treaty-based format: The so-called Quadruple Alliance of Napoleon's opponents formed the core of the emerging European state system and at the same time laid the foundation for the congress system that began after 1815. According to this system, the great powers were to meet at fixed times to jointly solve pan-European problems:

[...] the High Contracting Parties have agreed to renew their meetings at fixed periods [...] for the purpose of consulting upon their common interests, and for the consideration of the measures which [...] shall be considered the most salutary for the repose and prosperity of Nations, and for the maintenance of the Peace of Europe.²⁹³

Here, regular meetings of representatives of the great powers were planned, even if the formulation remains somewhat vague. In the aftermath of the Congress of Vienna, further

²⁹² Kupchan and Kupchan, “Concerts,” 123; see also Slantchev, “Territory,” 566.

²⁹³ “[...] les hautes parties contractantes sont convenues de renouveler, à des époques déterminées, [...] des réunions consacrées aux grands intérêts communs et à l'examen de mesures qui [...] seront jugées les plus salutaires pour le repos et la prospérité des peuples et pour le maintien de la paix de l'Europe,” *Traité d'alliance entre les Cours d'Autriche, de la Grande-Bretagne, de la Prusse et de la Russie, signé à Paris le 20 novembre 1815,* in *Le Congrès de Vienne et les traités de 1815, précédé et suivi des actes diplomatiques qui s'y rattachent, avec une introduction historique*, part 2, ed. Jean B. H. R. Capefigue (Paris: Amyot, 1863), 1636-1638, here 1637. Translation done by the author.

conferences of the great powers were organised, which took place at short intervals in the years up to 1822 - in Aachen (1818), Troppau/Opava (1820), Ljubljana (1821) and Verona (1822) political developments in Europe were discussed collectively.²⁹⁴ It seems likely that the “numerous confidential communications that took place between the five courts”²⁹⁵ were a form of institutionalisation in the sense of the formation of norms and modes of action, and their influence on the establishment of the Concert of Europe should not be underestimated.²⁹⁶ This is also how Kaelble and Kirsch see it: they consider, among other things, the establishment of European political and legal institutions and the increasing orientation of national governments towards European questions as an important part of the early Europeanisation, referring explicitly to the European congresses since 1815.²⁹⁷

The fact that the congress system – in contrast to the Concert of Europe – nevertheless played only a marginal role in the history of Europe of the nineteenth century is probably due to its short-lived nature: at Verona, only seven years after Vienna, consensus-building failed due to resistance from Great Britain, whereupon the congress system lost its pan-European character.²⁹⁸ Further developments towards an institutionalised European basis for communication and cooperation were thus prevented, although the opinions of historians vary greatly: Nichols delivers the most severe verdict: “For all practical purposes, the European Pentarchy died at Verona.”²⁹⁹ In contrast, Claude Conter highlights the persistence of the

²⁹⁴ Abbenhuis, *An Age of Neutrals*, 42.

²⁹⁵ “[...] *nombreuses communications confidentielles, qui ont eu lieu entre les cinq Cours*,” “Kongress von Verona IX. Circulaire finale”. Translation done by the author.

²⁹⁶ Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 31.

²⁹⁷ Hartmut Kaelble and Martin Kirsch, “Einleitung. Zur Europäisierung des Selbstverständnisses und der Gesellschaft der Europäer im 19. und 20. Jahrhundert,” in *Selbstverständnis und Gesellschaft der Europäer. Aspekte der sozialen und kulturellen Europäisierung im späten 19. und 20. Jahrhundert*, ed. Hartmut Kaelble and Martin Kirsch (Frankfurt a.M.: Peter Lang, 2008), 11-26, here 17.

²⁹⁸ Lappenküper, “Frühformen,” 128-129.

²⁹⁹ Nichols, *The European Pentarchy*, “ 135.

European congress system until the Congress of Berlin in 1878 and concludes that it was a successful instrument of European politics, though not well-liked by intellectuals.³⁰⁰

Ultimately, the verdict on the congresses hinges on the viewpoint in question – the reactionary, interventionist resolutions have often been criticised, as has the early failure of the joint conferences.³⁰¹ But however the congress policy is evaluated, it is evident that since the Congress of Vienna the idea of a common, consensual policy had taken root. Until World War I, the Concert of Europe remained the authoritative political framework, if not itself an institution for the way European states dealt with each other: “the Concert idea became the collective conscience of the European great powers.”³⁰² Conter again goes a step further, describing the Concert as a diplomatic system functioning as a quasi-European institution of peacekeeping.³⁰³

What is difficult to discern in these early forms of continental cooperation is a direct commitment to “Europe” as an idea or a topos in politics. Prussia, for example, was definitely understood as part of the European Pentarchy and was involved in all the alliances and congresses mentioned above. Yet the term “*Europa*” was first mentioned in the minutes of the Prussian Ministry of State (1817-1934/38) in 1843 – the only time it was mentioned in the period from 1817 to 1848!³⁰⁴ Just how present an explicitly European self-perception was in

³⁰⁰ “[...] *durchaus erfolgreiches, wenn auch von den Intellektuellen wenig geschätztes Instrument der Europapolitik*,” Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 31. Translation done by the author.

³⁰¹ Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 32.

³⁰² Elrod, “The Concert of Europe,” 168.

³⁰³ “[...] *jenes Diplomaten-system, dass als quasi-europäische Institution der Friedenssicherung fungierte*,” Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 31; Hantsch comes to a similar conclusion, he implies an institutionalisation of the Concert of Europe by referring to it as the areopag of great powers (“*Areopag der Großmächte*”), Hantsch, “Metternich,” 197. Translation done by the author.

³⁰⁴ Interestingly, the session in question was not about balance or great power policy, but about a postage tax to be adapted to the regulations of the other European states, “Sitzung des Staatsministeriums am 28. Juni 1843,” in *Die Protokolle des Preussischen Staatsministeriums 1817–1934/38*, 3: June 9, 1840, to March 14, 1848, Berlin-Brandenburgischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Hildesheim: Olms-Weidmann, 2000), 156.

the other governments remains to be seen, although historians such as Conter are convinced that a shared European consciousness³⁰⁵ developed in the course of the Congress of Vienna.

Conclusion

The characteristics of the political system in Europe presented above have shown that spaces (and constraints) for increased cooperation between the most important European states emerged in the first half of the nineteenth century. The resulting intensification of the cooperation between European states³⁰⁶ can therefore be understood as an early form of integration. In summary, the three aspects discussed could be correlated as follows: in post-Napoleonic Europe, the main *objective* of the Pentarchy was internal and external stability, which encouraged their cooperation for peacekeeping; the *implementation* of these political goal took the form of a pan-European balance of powers as the guiding principle of foreign policy; this policy underwent a temporary *institutionalisation* in the form of the Congress System, although it relied on the less specific framework of the Concert of Europe after 1822.

The question formulated above – “Europe as a Pentarchy?” – thus has its justification, and it contrasts narratives such as Girault’s: the history of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries compels him to assert that Europe is “damned to division and inner conflict”.³⁰⁷ I do not agree with this view (though the statement is probably formulated in a deliberately strong manner), considering the political developments presented here. It is true that the Pentarchy never developed a complex set of rules, but remained at the level of consensual deliberation, but this by no means meant that Europe became a continent completely torn apart by national interests. In my opinion, the emergence of the nation-state and the construction of the European Concert

³⁰⁵ “[...] *gemeineuropäisches Bewusstsein*,” Conter, “Europakonstruktivisten,” 31. Translation done by the author.

³⁰⁶ “[...] *immer engere Zusammenarbeit europäischer Staaten*,” Zandonella, “Europäische Integration”. Translation done by the author.

³⁰⁷ “*Ist Europa wirklich zur Teilung und zu inneren Konflikten verdammt? Seine Geschichte des 19. und der ersten Hälfte des 20. Jahrhunderts scheint zu einem Ja zu zwingen*,” Girault, “Das Europa der Historiker,” 63; Kaelble makes a similar argument, see Kaelble, *Europäer über Europa*, 57-58. Translation done by the author.

or Pentarchy as a political institution should be seen as (partly) parallel developments that shaped European integration in the nineteenth century for decades.

Various important developments, especially cultural, social or economic ones, have been excluded from this work, although they had a determining influence on the formation of European institutions and supranational organisations – the main reason for this is the limited scope of this paper, which is restricted to the political level. Numerous open questions remain and call for further research, regarding, for example, the European sentiment of nineteenth century governments and their successors: one issue already noted above is the perception or Europeanisation of the self-image of cabinets, ministers and heads of state. Also unresolved is the continuity of the European cooperation policy shaped by the Pentarchy after the Crimean War into the twentieth century – are there, for example, ideational influences or influences shaped by political traditions of the Concert of Europe on the modern integration process up to the European Union?³⁰⁸

As this short paper has shown, diplomatic history and the history of international relations in the nineteenth century remain an important pillar of the study of modern European integration. I believe that to understand its preconditions, its early development and the preceding systems of diplomatic and intergovernmental exchange is ever more important in times of growing nationalist movements and renewed imperialist aggression in Europe. This paper has shown that integration processes unfolded much earlier than the narrative of the post-World War II integration suggests – at a time which is predominantly associated with the emergence of the nation-state instead of institutionalised inter-state cooperation on a European level. It is my

³⁰⁸ The insufficient embeddedness of the history of the EU in the European history of the modern era is denounced by Kaiser, see Kaiser, “From Isolation to Centrality,” 47, 50.

sincere hope that further research on these matters will allow us to further extend, question and adjust the historiography and narratives of European integration.

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